

Actions to halt biodiversity loss generally benefit the climate

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1 Abstract

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3 The two most urgent and interlinked environmental challenges humanity faces are climate change and
4 biodiversity loss. We are entering a pivotal decade for both the international biodiversity and climate
5 change agendas with the sharpening of ambitious strategies and targets by the Convention on Biological
6 Diversity and the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. Within their respective
7 Conventions, the two biodiversity and climate interlinked challenges have been addressed separately.
8 There is evidence that conservation actions that halt, slow or reverse biodiversity loss can simultaneously
9 slow anthropogenic mediated climate change significantly. This review highlights conservation actions
10 which have the largest potential for mitigation of climate change. We note that conservation actions have
11 mainly synergistic benefits and few antagonistic trade-offs with climate change mitigation. Specifically,
12 we identify direct co-benefits in 14 out of the 21 action targets of the draft post-2020 global biodiversity
13 framework of the Convention on Biological Diversity, notwithstanding the many indirect links that can as
14 well support both biodiversity conservation and climate change mitigation. These relationships are
15 context and scale-dependent; therefore, we showcase examples of local biodiversity conservation actions
16 that can be incentivized, guided and prioritized by global objectives and targets. The close interlinkages
17 between biodiversity, climate change mitigation, other nature's contributions to people and good quality
18 of life are seldom as integrated as they should be in management and policy. This review aims to re-
19 emphasize timeously the vital relationships between biodiversity conservation actions and climate change
20 mitigation, prior to major Conferences of Parties that are about to negotiate strategic frameworks and
21 international goals for the decades to come.

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25 **Keywords:** biodiversity conservation, climate change mitigation, Convention on Biological Diversity,
26 restoration, nature-based solutions, carbon sequestration

1. Introduction

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The value of nature in mitigating climate change is well recognized and quantified globally. More than 30% of anthropogenic CO₂ emissions are re-absorbed annually into the land surface (Friedlingstein et al., 2020) through forest regrowth, enhanced photosynthetic CO₂ uptake and sequestration (Pugh et al., 2019; Ahlström et al. 2015, Schimel et al., 2015). A further ca. 25% of anthropogenic CO₂ emissions is absorbed by the ocean (Friedlingstein et al., 2020; IPCC, 2019), due to both CO₂ dissolution in the ocean and the organic carbon cycle driven largely by photosynthesis, carbon sequestration in coastal vegetated habitats and the biological pump that moves carbon from the upper ocean layers to the deep ocean waters and ocean floor sediments. These powerful natural sinks are currently by far the leading natural mitigation processes globally. Their carbon sequestration potential can be protected, and even enhanced, both through ecosystem management on land, and in the oceans, though not without risks in each case. In the UNFCCC (United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change) and CBD (Convention on Biological Diversity), the concept of nature-based solutions has been proposed as a way to harness natural processes to help solve the climate challenge and reduce the risk to biodiversity in particular, while providing other co-benefits.

Implementing nature-based solutions therefore aims to make use of the powerful interactions between the climate system, the oceans, the land, and nature within these realms. Crucially, this needs to be managed without compromising the many nature's contributions to people (NCPs) (Girardin et al., 2021). The potential effects of biodiversity conservation on the climate system include the enhanced sequestration of anthropogenic CO₂ on land and in the oceans, reduction of greenhouse gas (GHG) fluxes to the atmosphere associated with ecosystem management (e.g., wildfires, land cover change and agricultural practices), and increasing the reflectivity of the land surface (albedo change). The central question we address in this paper is the extent to which actions taken to halt or reverse biodiversity loss have consequences for these climate change mitigation processes, and how, when and where the form and strength of such links vary.

The last decade has seen increased concerns about biodiversity loss, with multiple lines of evidence that nature and its contributions to people are declining globally at unprecedented rates (Diaz et al., 2019; IPBES, 2019). National level responses have not been at the level of required actions, partially achieving only a handful of the Aichi Biodiversity Targets of the CBD Strategic Plan for Biodiversity 2011–2020 (Butchart et al., 2019; SCBD, 2005). Thus, there are high expectations for the upcoming CBD fifteenth Conference of the Parties (CBD COP 15) which will be held at the end of 2021 in Kunming (China) to finalize a new set of well-defined goals and targets that would incentivize strong and ambitious actions to reverse the loss of biodiversity.

66 In the first draft of the post-2020 global biodiversity framework of the CBD released in July 2021 (CBD,
67 2021), there is a dedicated target on mitigation and adaptation to climate change – “*Target 8: Minimize*
68 *the impact of climate change on biodiversity, contribute to mitigation and adaptation through ecosystem-*
69 *based approaches, contributing at least 10 GtCO₂e per year to global mitigation efforts, and ensure that*
70 *all mitigation and adaptation efforts avoid negative impacts on biodiversity*”. The UNFCCC Paris
71 Agreement, under Decision 1/CP.21, made a singular reference to biodiversity where Parties noted in the
72 preamble “*the importance of ensuring the integrity of all ecosystems, including oceans, and the protection*
73 *of biodiversity, recognized by some cultures as Mother Earth, and noting the importance for some of the*
74 *concept of “climate justice”, when taking action to address climate change*”. Although we see a step
75 forward in the recognition that biodiversity and climate change are interconnected by decision- and
76 policy-makers in these two separate Conventions, the two issues are still largely addressed separately and
77 in an unbalanced manner.

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79 Based on the work conducted for section 5 of the scientific outcome of the IPBES-IPCC co-sponsored
80 workshop on biodiversity and climate change (Pörtner et al., 2021), we review recent scientific evidence
81 relevant to assessing potential synergy between slowing and halting biodiversity loss and avoiding
82 dangerous climate change. To what extent are these most urgent and important challenges facing
83 humanity today interlinked by mechanistic links and feedbacks? Here, we focus on links between
84 biodiversity conservation actions and climate change mitigation. Such actions and interventions are
85 context and scale-dependent; therefore, we showcase examples of local biodiversity conservation actions
86 that can be incentivized, guided and prioritized by global objectives and targets given all actions matter.
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88 2. Post-2020 biodiversity goals have strong potential co-benefits for 89 climate change mitigation

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91 Many policy measures designed to address biodiversity loss and degradation of NCPs have potential co-
92 benefits with climate change mitigation (Girardin et al., 2021). The level of such co-benefits largely
93 depends on the processes affected and the nature component involved. Just as it is important to
94 distinguish between carbon capture (e.g., by photosynthesis), storage (e.g., in the bodies of organisms)
95 and sequestration (e.g., protected from microbial activity in soils and sediments for periods of centuries
96 to millennia) (Bax et al., 2021; Siegel et al., 2021), understanding differences between sinks and feedbacks
97 also greatly aids understanding of climate and biodiversity interactions. Albedo feedbacks (and other
98 feedbacks arising from biophysical processes at the land surface) on climate may be an important
99 component of climate change, but they are currently ignored by UNFCCC guidelines in accounting for the
100 climate benefits of actions taken in support of climate change mitigation (Duveiller et al., 2020; Perugini
101 et al., 2017; Jia et al., 2019).

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Carbon sinks are the result of net carbon capture and storage. Such sinks can be mediated by physicochemical (e.g., direct oceanic uptake of CO₂ via the solubility pump, which leads to ocean acidification) or biological processes (photosynthesis and subsequent storage of the assimilated carbon). The sink is usually *in situ* (e.g., forests, peatlands, agricultural soils or mangroves) but may sometimes act by exporting the carbon elsewhere (e.g., kelp forests exporting to deep seas, or the marine vertical biological pump), and a portion of the carbon is usually sequestered. Many natural carbon sinks and the capacity of processes driving those sinks are reduced by climate change, thereby exacerbating climate change further (positive feedback; Arneeth et al. 2010). In contrast, some carbon sinks, such as polar continental shelves and boreal forests (taiga) increase with climate change, so they work as a negative feedback strengthening mitigation (Zhu et al., 2016; Piao et al., 2006). When biodiversity conservation measures and nature-based solutions concern natural carbon sinks having both large size and negative feedbacks on climate change, they can be powerful in regulating climate.

The first draft of the post-2020 global biodiversity framework provides 21 action-oriented targets for 2030 which aim to contribute to the 2050 Vision for Biodiversity. Most of the framework targets have direct or indirect impacts on climate change mitigation (Table 1), even though they were not primarily designed with this intention. Here, we highlight a subset of biodiversity measures that are shown to have impacts on the climate system, based on potential contributions to carbon capture, storage, and sequestration, the albedo effect, and non-CO₂ GHG fluxes.

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Table 1: Action targets for 2030, from the first draft of the post-2020 global biodiversity framework of the CBD (please refer to CBD (2021) for the full and exact wording of the targets), and examples of biodiversity measures with impacts on climate change mitigation (see main text). The effects of biodiversity measures on climate change mitigation are colour coded (see legend), as well as the reliability of achieving the mitigation outcome. The colour coding reflects expert judgement based on scientific literature (see Table S1 and main text). Target 8 is not colour coded as it is the outcome of all other targets, as documented in the table. (T: Target).

Contribution to climate change mitigation		Reliability of the mitigation outcome (chance of achievement)	
	High		
	Medium		
	Unresolved, insufficient evidence		
	Low		
	Indirect positive		
	Loose or non-existent link		

Post-2020 Action targets for 2030	Biodiversity measures (and corresponding section in the main text)	Contribution to climate change mitigation	Reliability of mitigation outcome
Reducing threats to biodiversity			
T1. Biodiversity-inclusive spatial planning addressing land/sea use change, retaining intact and wilderness areas	2.1 Avoiding deforestation		
	2.1 Avoiding degradation of permafrost areas		
T2. Restoration of at least 20% of degraded ecosystems, ensured connectivity and focus on priority areas	2.1 Reforestation, avoided degradation of forests		
	2.1 Coastal restoration		
	2.1 Restoring degraded semi-arid ecosystems		
	2.1 Restoring inland wetlands		
	2.1 Biodiversity offsets		
T3. Well connected and effective system of protected areas, at least 30% of the planet	2.2 Expanding networks of protected areas and corridors		
T4. Recovery and conservation of species of fauna and flora	2.3 Rewilding with large terrestrial mammals		
	2.3 Rebuilding marine megafauna		
T5. Sustainable, legal and safe harvesting, trade and use of wild species	2.4 Sustainable fishing		
T6. Prevention and reduced rate of introductions, control or eradication of invasive alien species			
T7. Reduced pollution from all sources, including excess nutrients, pesticides, plastic waste	2.5 Reducing pollution from excess nutrients		
T8. Impacts of climate change on biodiversity minimized, contributions to climate change mitigation, adaptation			

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Post-2020 Action targets for 2030	Biodiversity measures (and corresponding section in the maintext)		Contribution to climate change mitigation	Reliability of mitigation outcome
Meeting people's needs through sustainable use and benefit-sharing				
T9. Ensured benefits, incl. food security, medicines, and livelihoods, through sustainable management of wild species	2.4	Sustainable harvesting of wild species		
T10. All areas under agriculture, aquaculture and forestry are managed sustainably, through biodiversity conservation and sustainable use, and increased productivity and resilience	2.6	Biodiversity-friendly agricultural systems		
	2.6	Intensive vs less intensive agriculture		
	2.6	Combatting woody plant encroachment		
T11. Contribution to regulation of air quality, hazards and extreme events and quality and quantity of water	2			
T12. Increased area of, access to, and benefits from green/blue spaces for health and well-being in urban areas	2.7	Increasing benefits from biodiversity and green/blue spaces in urban areas		
T13. Ensured access to and the fair and equitable sharing of benefits from genetic resources and traditional knowledge				
Tools and solutions for implementation and mainstreaming				
T14. Biodiversity values integrated into policies, regulations, planning, development, poverty reduction, accounts and assessments at all levels and across all sectors	2.8	Mainstreaming biodiversity		
T15. Dependencies and impacts on biodiversity assessed in all businesses, negative impacts halved, for sustainable extraction and production, sourcing and supply chains, use and disposal	2.4	Sustainable food production and supply chains		
T16. People are informed and enabled to make responsible choices, to halve the waste and reduce overconsumption of food and other materials where relevant	2.9	Sustainable consumption patterns		
T17. Preventing, managing or controlling potential adverse impacts of biotechnology on biodiversity and human health				
T18. Redirect, repurpose, reform or eliminate incentives harmful for biodiversity in a just and equitable way	2.10	Eliminating incentives harmful for biodiversity		
T19. Increasing financial resources from all sources and flows to developing countries, and ensuring capacity-building, technology transfer and scientific cooperation				
T20. Relevant knowledge, incl. traditional, indigenous and local knowledge, guides the management of biodiversity by promoting awareness, education and research				
T21. Equitable and effective participation in decision-making by indigenous peoples and local communities, respecting their rights over lands, territories and resources				

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2.1 Restoring degraded natural areas and retaining existing intact wilderness areas (Targets 1 and 2)

Restoring degraded natural areas is a flagship target of the post-2020 global biodiversity framework of the CBD and put in the spotlight by the UN Decade on Ecosystem Restoration (2021-2030). Restoration is particularly critical where natural systems are so damaged that spontaneous recovery is unlikely or too slow compared to their degradation rate. Initially designed for protecting nature and its contributions to people, restoration programs provide opportunities for climate change mitigation, if selected ecosystems are both rich in species and potentially large carbon sinks.

147 ***Reforestation, avoided deforestation and degradation of forests***

148 The large-scale degradation of tropical and subtropical forests and woodlands is well documented (Baldi
149 & Jobbágy, 2012; Baldi et al., 2013), mainly driven by agricultural expansion and biofuel production (e.g.,
150 Laurance et al., 2014; Estes et al., 2016; van Eijck et al., 2014) and negatively impacting both biodiversity
151 and carbon stocks (Mackey et al., 2020). Tropical deforestation contributed to almost one fifth of global
152 anthropogenic GHG emissions during the 1990s (~5.5 GtCO₂e yr⁻¹; Gullison et al., 2007). Recent satellite
153 remote sensing studies highlighted that the area of degraded tropical forest could be well equal or even
154 exceed the area of deforestation (Bullock et al., 2020; Matricardi et al., 2020), with an increasing trend.
155 The above-ground carbon losses associated with degradation have been estimated to increase estimates
156 of gross deforestation losses by between 25% to possibly more than 600% (Baccini et al., 2017; Maxwell
157 et al., 2019; Pearson et al., 2017). Additional losses from soils are unknown. Dryland forest and savanna
158 deforestation and degradation have proceeded over many decades, threatening carbon stocks and the
159 rich biodiversity in South America (e.g., Chaco and Cerrado systems; Mustin et al., 2017), Asia (Tölle et al.,
160 2017) and Australia (e.g., Eucalypt woodlands; Queensland Department of Science, Information
161 Technology and Innovation, 2017), with high biodiversity African woodlands (Kier et al., 2005) having
162 some of the highest deforestation rates in the world (e.g., 2500 - 3000 km² yr⁻¹ in Zambia; Vinya et al.,
163 2011).

164
165 International efforts to incentivize the slowing and ultimate avoidance of deforestation were accelerated
166 with the adoption of the REDD+ mechanism (reducing emissions from deforestation and forest
167 degradation in developing countries) by the UNFCCC in 2007, which provides a significant opportunity to
168 align national climate change mitigation and biodiversity goals (Johnson et al., 2019). Recent evidence
169 shows that the REDD+ has been effective in some regions, for example, leading to the avoidance of 1.5
170 (+/-0.4) GtCO₂e emissions from tropical forest in Brazil alone, between 2006 and 2017 (West et al., 2019).
171 However, barriers to full implementation of the mechanism are limiting its effectiveness in some tropical
172 regions such as in Indonesia (Ekawati et al., 2019) and in Africa (Gizachew et al., 2017).

173 Reforestation or restoration of degraded forests and woodlands with indigenous species plays a role in
174 addressing losses of biodiversity and NCPs, including through recovering the soil carbon stocks of these
175 ecosystems (e.g., Sileshi, 2016). Reforesting up to 3.69 million km² of degraded tropical forest (less than
176 half the potentially reforestable area) could generate a potential carbon uptake of 5.5 GtCO₂e yr⁻¹ by 2030,
177 and contribute to the conservation of hundreds of threatened forest-dependent vertebrate species
178 (Kemppinen et al., 2020). Spatially targeted reforestation efforts could re-establish forest habitat
179 continuity with outside positive impacts (e.g. Atlantic Forest; Newmark et al., 2017; Strassburg et al.,
180 2018). Financial incentives currently encourage reforestation using monoculture plantations of non-
181 indigenous species (e.g., Lewis et al., 2019), and some large scale silviculture programs are planned (e.g.,
182 Brazil; Mustin et al., 2017; Ethiopia; Pistorius et al., 2017), but this practice may be associated with
183 significant risks for nature and its contributions to people (Reisman-Berman et al., 2019).

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185 ***Coastal restoration***

186 Coastal habitats and ecosystems (e.g., mangroves, seagrass, salt marshes, coral reefs) are highly
187 productive areas, harboring large amounts of biological diversity, and providing valuable ecosystem
188 services (e.g., water quality, carbon sequestration, food, livelihoods, cultural services, and coastal
189 protection; Mcleod et al., 2011). Coastal ecosystems are exposed to increase in temperature, acidification,
190 sea level rise, salinification, and exposure to intensified storms (IPCC, 2014; Hoegh-Guldberg et al., 2018).
191 Urbanisation and coastal hardening further exert a strong pressure with increasing clustering of cities and
192 other forms of development along the coasts (Barragán & de Andrés, 2015; Liu et al., 2018; Loke et al.,
193 2019). The range of many coastal ecosystems has been contracting as a result (e.g., mangroves (Babcock
194 et al., 2019); coral reefs (Oppenheimer et al., 2019); seagrass (Waycott et al., 2009)) or moving
195 (Poloczanska et al., 2016). Critically, the destruction and the degradation of these habitats have led to
196 reduced 'blue carbon' stocks as biomass accumulation slows and soils are exposed to increased oxidation
197 of organic deposits (Mcleod et al., 2011). While the total sequestration of carbon is much lower in coastal
198 systems than in terrestrial forests, the amount per unit area is typically much higher (Donato et al., 2011).

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200 The success and costs of restoration options has varied between ecosystems. Mangrove forests are
201 capable of storing and sequestering a substantial proportion of carbon in both their biomass and soil
202 substrates (Sanderman et al., 2018) even when fringing dense urban development areas, as demonstrated
203 in Singapore (Friess et al., 2015). Bayraktarov et al. (2016) reviewed restoration costs across a range of
204 coastal ecosystems and found that coral reefs and seagrass beds were among the most expensive
205 ecosystems to meaningfully restore, whilst mangrove restoration projects were the least expensive per
206 unit area.

207

208 ***Avoiding degradation of permafrost areas***

209 Northern and mountain permafrost contains twice as much carbon as the atmosphere and about four
210 times more than all the carbon emitted by human activity in modern times, and most of it occurs in
211 perennially frozen soils and deposits (Ciais et al., 2013; Schuur et al., 2011; Tarnocai et al., 2009). The
212 degradation of permafrost wetlands due to climatic warming and the minerals extraction industry
213 (Opekunova et al., 2018; Peterson, 2001) leads to oxidation and the release of the carbon stored in soils.
214 Such changes are very likely to impact species richness negatively due to habitat loss and reduced water
215 quality, and increase risk of extinctions of wetland endemic and dependent species (Shin et al., 2019).
216 Better management of permafrost wetlands, preservation of undamaged peatlands and restoration of
217 degraded areas will help in maintaining their biodiversity and keeping carbon locked in the ground (Anisha
218 et al., 2020). This requires stopping damaging practices involving drainage or excavation of peatlands and
219 taking action to rewet and restore degraded peatlands (Avagyan et al., 2017). Successful management

220 plans include the Long-Term Gravel Pad Reclamation in Alaska (Peterson, 2001) and the Strategic Plan for
221 peatland conservation and wise use in Mongolia (Ariunbaatar et al., 2017). In northern high-latitude
222 ecosystems, introducing large herbivores increases snow density and hence decreases the insulation
223 strength of snow during winter and exposes permafrost to colder temperatures, thereby preventing or
224 decreasing CH₄ release from permafrost thawing. In addition, large herbivores provide summer albedo
225 increase by selective foraging and additional carbon sequestration by soil (Cahoon et al., 2012; Falk et al.,
226 2015; Schmitz et al., 2018; te Beest et al., 2016). Such ecosystem management practices could be scaled
227 up in Arctic permafrost areas as an ecosystem-based option to support global climate change mitigation
228 strategy (Figure 1 and Case study 11 in Table S3).

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230 ***Restoring degraded semi-arid ecosystems***

231 Degradation of semi-arid ecosystems is often associated with significant losses of soil, and the carbon that
232 is held in that soil (e.g., Chappell et al., 2016, 2019). Reversal of soil degradation linked to desertification
233 trends has long been a focus of the UN Convention to Combat Desertification. Rebuilding soil (especially)
234 and plant carbon stocks in semi-arid regions is seen as a potentially significant contribution to mitigation
235 of CO₂ emissions because of their large extent, and to both interannual variability and trend in the land
236 carbon sink (Ahlström et al., 2015). But this view has also seen contradictory claims of efficacy in the last
237 decade (Yusuf et al., 2015). The capacity of restoring degraded semi-arid systems using land use
238 management approaches is thus somewhat contested (Gosnell et al., 2020). Many semi-arid systems
239 around the world have been observed as having “greening” trends (Fensholt et al., 2012). This has been
240 linked to the effects of rising atmospheric CO₂ in increasing plant water-use efficiency (Donohue et al.,
241 2013), thereby increasing the competitive advantage of woody plants over grasses and increasing woody
242 cover in these ecosystems. Global analysis of remote-sensed data suggests that greening is generally
243 associated with soil drying as a result of higher plant cover (Deng et al., 2020), and woody encroachment
244 also reduces grazing potential (Anadón et al., 2014).

245

246 ***Restoring inland wetlands***

247 Inland wetland ecosystems provide vital services, such as freshwater and food, water purification, and
248 flood prevention that humans have been benefiting for agriculture, aquaculture, and urban development
249 at the cost of a widespread degradation (IPBES, 2018). Wetlands are important for global carbon
250 sequestration, but their disturbance could result in increases of GHGs (Adhikari et al., 2009). Conversion,
251 drainage and degradation of tropical wetlands and peatlands are important drivers of current increases
252 in the atmospheric concentration of CH₄ (Shukla et al., 2019). Irrigated rice cultivation, which takes place
253 mostly in former wetlands, is also an important contributor to CH₄ in the atmosphere (Shukla et al., 2019),
254 noting that many irrigated rice areas are Ramsar sites for the protection of endangered species (Xi et al.,
255 2020).

256
257 The protection and restoration of wetlands and peatlands is expected to reduce net carbon loss to the
258 atmosphere and provide continued or restored natural CO₂ removal (IPCC, 2019). Reducing annual
259 emissions from peatland restoration could mitigate 0.15 to 0.81 GtCO₂e y⁻¹ up to 2050 (Couwenberg et
260 al., 2009; Griscom et al., 2017; IPCC, 2019). There has been significant knowledge gained over the last
261 decade on wetland drainage and rewetting practices (IPCC, 2013), however, there are still high
262 uncertainties as to the carbon storage and flux rates, in particular the balance between CH₄ sources and
263 CO₂ sinks (IPCC, 2019; Spencer et al., 2016). Recent evidence (Chapter in IPCC, 2019) shows that tropical
264 wetland CH₄ emissions are underestimated, perhaps by a factor of two. One suggestion is that estimates
265 do not account for release by tree stems (Pangala et al., 2017). However, several authors have concluded
266 that agriculture is a more probable source of increased emissions, and particularly from rice and livestock
267 production systems in the tropics, which is consistent with inventory data (Wolf et al., 2017; Patra et al.,
268 2016; Schaefer et al., 2016). For peatlands, while models show mixed results for their role as future sink
269 (Spahni et al., 2013; Chaudhary et al., 2017; Ise et al., 2008), a study that used extensive historical data
270 sets to project change under future warming scenarios suggested that the currently global peatland sink
271 could increase slightly until 2100 and decline thereafter (Gallego-Sala et al., 2018).

272 273 ***Biodiversity offsets***

274 Biodiversity offsetting is the practice of mitigating the negative impacts of developments on biodiversity
275 (e.g., mining, urban/housing development, agricultural expansion) by restoring the biodiversity, or setting
276 aside areas for protection, elsewhere in remote sites. The mechanism by which the practice of biodiversity
277 offsetting could also mitigate climate change is through storage of carbon in biomass and soils in newly
278 developed or restored habitats, either in public or private (often agricultural) lands. Much of the research
279 on biodiversity offsets is concentrated in North America, Western Europe, and Australasia (Bull & Strange,
280 2018) and focuses on whether the no net loss (NNL) principle has been met in the offset program (e.g.,
281 Ermgassen et al., 2019). There are 12,983 listed biodiversity offsets under NLL principles implemented
282 across 37 countries, predominantly forest ecosystems, covering about 153,679 km² (Bull & Strange, 2018).
283 However, a recent review indicated that only one third of biodiversity offsets met the NNL principle. None
284 of the forest projects achieved NNL, whereas offsetting in wetlands was found to be more successful
285 (Ermgassen et al., 2019). This widespread failure raises concerns regarding the capacity of existing
286 biodiversity offsetting implementation to mitigate climate change. There is also little evidence of the
287 resilience of these offsets to climate change, and the trade-offs between biodiversity offsets, carbon
288 storage and other NCPs have rarely been assessed (Sonter et al., 2020).

289
290 Where biodiversity offsets limit local people's access to, or loss of benefits from, the biodiversity and NCPs
291 on which their livelihoods depend, it can have negative impacts on climate change adaptation (Jones et
292 al., 2019). Applying the NNL principle to offsetting programs will not necessarily minimize the trade-offs

293 and disconnects between the loss of local benefits from biodiversity, with gains in remote or global
294 benefits. Such trade-offs are likely to be avoided or addressed more appropriately if the type and
295 distribution of NCPs are considered in the offsetting process along with the NNL.

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297 **2.2 Implementing a well-connected and effective system of protected areas (Target 3)**

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299 ***Expanding the network of protected areas***

300 As of July 2021, protected areas cover 15.7% of terrestrial habitats and 7.7% of marine habitats (UNEP-
301 WCMC, 2021). There is increasing evidence that creating new protected areas and maintaining existing
302 ones can help mitigating climate change through carbon sequestration and storage on land (Soares-Filho
303 et al., 2010; UNEP, 2019; Dinerstein et al., 2020) and at sea (O’Leary et al., 2016; Roberts et al., 2017; Sala
304 et al., 2021). At sea, ecological representation and connectivity between marine protected areas would
305 require at least 30% of sea protected, with a focus on areas most affected by human activities (Roberts et
306 al., 2020). Most known, and nearly all measured examples of linking marine protection to climate change
307 mitigation are in coastal wetlands, yet the vast majority of ocean (and protected ocean) is deep water.
308 Though little studied, deep water ecosystems can hold considerable and important seabed carbon, such
309 as around remote islands and seamounts (Barnes et al 2019), Arctic and Antarctic continental shelves (see
310 Souster et al., 2020 and Bax et al., 2021, respectively). On land, it is estimated that current protected areas
311 store between 12% and 16% of land carbon stocks (Melillo et al., 2016; Dinerstein et al., 2020). To both
312 reverse biodiversity loss and stabilize the climate, Dinerstein et al. (2020) suggest that protected areas
313 should cover 50.4% of the terrestrial realm, storing a total of 1420 GtC. Interestingly, 92% of the area
314 needing protection for enhancing carbon storage and drawdown are covered by the area needed to
315 reverse biodiversity loss. Hannah et al. (2020) calculated that by limiting global warming to 2°C and
316 conserving 30% of the terrestrial surface, aggregate extinction risk would be more than halved relative to
317 a base case of unmitigated climate change and no increase in conserved areas. These studies, while
318 needing to be consolidated, emphasize the strong interlinkage between conservation, biodiversity, and
319 climate change mitigation.

320

321 ***Establishing ecological corridors***

322 Establishing ecological corridors through landscape conservation or ecoregion-based approaches is
323 essential to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of protected areas in fragmented landscapes and
324 seascapes (Dinerstein et al., 2017; Keeley et al., 2018; Littlefield et al., 2019). A large number of corridors
325 have carbon densities that approach or exceed those of the protected areas they connect, containing, for
326 example, 15% of the total unprotected aboveground carbon in the tropical region (Jantz et al., 2014).
327 Under the ‘Global Safety Net’ plan that aims to reverse biodiversity loss and increase carbon storage and
328 drawdown, only 4.3% of additional area (but based on 2.5km corridor width) would be required to connect

329 all current protected areas (Dinerstein et al., 2020). Hallmarks of successful connectivity conservation
330 includes community involvement, habitat priority setting, restoration actions, and environmental services
331 payments that satisfy tenets of climate-smart conservation, and improve the resilience of human and
332 ecological communities (Littlefield et al., 2019; Townsend & Masters, 2015). Progress in protecting and
333 restoring habitat connectivity has been slow (Keeley et al., 2018), and their climate benefits have not been
334 fully explored.

335

336 **2.3 Recovering and conserving wild species (Target 4)**

337

338 On land, rewilding includes fostering the regrowth of natural vegetation as well as the reintroduction of
339 native fauna, such as large predators and herbivores. Vegetation regrowth, especially naturally
340 regenerating trees and shrubs in rewilded areas, contributes to climate change mitigation by capturing
341 carbon dioxide and enhancing above-ground carbon pools. Animals have long been considered irrelevant
342 for carbon cycling in land ecosystems, simply because their biomass is orders of magnitude lower than
343 that of plants and microbes (Bar-On et al., 2018; Schmitz et al., 2018). This view is being challenged by an
344 increasing body of literature. Herbivory reduces above-ground live biomass, enhances light transfer into
345 the canopy, and increases nutrient input to the soil through impact on litter amount and quality. Herbivory
346 also affects canopy structure, ranging from shifts in the ratio of woody to herbaceous vegetation in
347 grasslands and savannas, to age structure and species composition in forests (Sankaran et al., 2013;
348 Schmitz et al., 2018; Tanentzap & Coomes, 2012). Cascading trophic effects triggered by top predators or
349 the largest herbivores propagate through food webs and reverberate through the functioning of whole
350 ecosystems, changing productivity and net carbon storage significantly (Malhi et al., 2016; Schuldt et al.,
351 2018). Carnivore-herbivore-plant interactions mediate soil and ecosystem carbon and nitrogen turnover
352 rates (Schmitz et al., 2018; Tanentzap & Coomes, 2012), thus affecting fundamental properties of the
353 terrestrial carbon cycle. The overall impact on carbon uptake is not yet well understood and likely will
354 differ between regions and ecosystem types.

355

356 At sea, marine mammals, sharks and big predatory fish have been severely overexploited for decades
357 (Myers & Worm, 2003; Roman, 2003), and are now the focus of many conservation programs around the
358 world. As for terrestrial mammals, the functional role of these emblematic species in the global carbon
359 cycle has often been neglected but recent studies show that these predators are important to consider
360 either as carbon sinks or mediators of carbon sequestration in the ocean (Atwood et al., 2015; Heithaus
361 et al., 2014; Lavery et al., 2010; Mariani et al., 2020; Passow & Carlson, 2012; Roman & McCarthy, 2010).
362 The role of animals, such as predators, has been particularly scrutinized in marine vegetated coastal
363 habitats, identified as carbon-rich ecosystems, where predators are essential to control the abundance of
364 herbivores and bioturbators which in turn impact the canopy height, root and shoot densities of the
365 macrophytes, all characteristics playing a role in carbon capture and storage in plants, sequestration in

366 sediments, and particle trapping (Atwood et al., 2015). Trophic downgrading triggered by the loss of
367 predators can lead to the complete loss of salt marshes and seagrass habitats (Atwood et al., 2015), or
368 severe reduction in the density of kelp forests (Wilmers et al., 2012). The case of the green turtle, a
369 vulnerable and emblematic species, poses an interesting conservation challenge, as this seagrass grazer,
370 when at high densities as a result of intense rewilding programs, and in the absence of predators
371 (overexploited sharks), can overgraze and deplete seagrass beds (Heithaus et al., 2014).

372
373 In offshore waters, whales contribute to the biological pump, i.e., the removal of carbon from the euphotic
374 zone to the deep sea and sea bottom where it can be sequestered for several centuries or more (Passow
375 & Carlson, 2012). While the sinking of whales' carcasses is negligible compared to other drivers of the
376 biological pump, it serves as a synergistic positive outcome of rebuilding programs (Pershing et al., 2010).
377 Possibly more important is the role played by whales' faecal plumes in fertilizing surface waters in
378 allochthonous limiting nutrients, iron in particular, boosting primary production and thereby capturing
379 atmospheric carbon through to the ocean biological pump (Lavery et al., 2010; Roman & McCarthy, 2010).

380

381 **2.4 Ensuring sustainable harvesting of wild species, food production and supply chains** 382 **(Targets 5, 9 and 15)**

383
384 Human population is projected to grow to 10 billion or more by 2050 and so there will be a need to
385 produce more food from land and sea, as well as to reduce wastes substantially.

386
387 Agriculture is a main driver of biodiversity loss on land (Green et al., 2005; Newbold et al., 2015, 2016),
388 largely through conversion of natural ecosystems to agriculture, with conversion for livestock farming
389 being the main driver (Crist et al., 2017). Interventions to improve the biodiversity status of agricultural
390 land and food supply chains include: a) less intensive farming practices, such as agroecology (Albrecht et
391 al., 2020; Tittonell et al., 2020; 2.6), though if this results in lower productivity, this can simply exacerbate
392 the clearance of natural ecosystems for agriculture (Phalan et al., 2011); b) sustainable intensification of
393 production (Pretty et al., 2018), which allows land to be freed for nature conservation (Balmford et al.,
394 2018; 2.6) or c) demand-side changes in the food system supply chain, such as dietary change toward
395 more plant-based diets with less meat and dairy (Bajželj et al., 2014; Alexander et al., 2016) and reducing
396 food loss and waste (Gustavsson et al., 2011; Alexander et al., 2017) which reduces demand for products
397 that use a lot of land (Hayek et al., 2021). These interventions to improve the biodiversity status of
398 agricultural land also have significant climate change mitigation and adaptation benefits with mitigation
399 potentials ranging from 0.1 to 8 GtCO₂e y⁻¹, and adaptation benefits accruing to up to 2.3 billion people
400 (Smith et al., 2020a).

401

402 Focusing of new aquaculture activities on low trophic level species as well as broadening the range of
403 species cultivated, especially from unfed or environmentally friendly integrated aquaculture systems, are
404 ways to increase global seafood production with minimal impact to the environment and biodiversity
405 (SAPEA, 2017). Expanded cultivation of seaweed offers a potential route to reducing coastal
406 eutrophication (Xiao et al., 2017), avoiding related GHG emissions, sequestering CO₂ in sediments (Duarte
407 et al., 2017) and producing food, animal feed which reduces methane production by ruminants and a
408 range of other products such as bioplastics (Ditchburn & Carballeira, 2019). Optimal places to expand such
409 seaweed cultivation and their environmental carrying capacity need, however, to be identified (Froehlich
410 et al., 2019).

411
412 Fishing is a major driver of biodiversity loss in the ocean both as a result of overexploitation, bycatch and
413 destruction of habitats (Rogers et al., 2020; IPBES, 2019). Fishing can also impact carbon fluxes, by
414 exporting ocean carbon to land and ultimately to the atmosphere that would otherwise be sequestered
415 in the deep sea for centuries or more (Mariani et al., 2020; Sala et al., 2021). Downward passive transport
416 of carbon occurs through sinking of dead carcasses, faecal pellets of fish and invertebrates, and this has
417 been shown to be a significant contribution to the biological pump. For example, it was estimated that
418 fisheries targeting large pelagic fish have released a minimum of 0.73 GtCO₂e since 1950 (Mariani et al.,
419 2020). In the Southern Ocean, krill (*Euphausia superba*) is estimated to be responsible for about 35% of
420 current export of carbon to the ocean floor in the marginal ice zone (Belcher et al., 2019). In addition,
421 fishing impacts the biological pump by extracting organisms that realize active diurnal vertical migration
422 (DVM), feeding at the surface at night, and then joining the deeper mesopelagic domain during daytime
423 where they produce faecal pellets. The flux of carbon driven by DVM is estimated to be 3.85 ± 0.5 GtCO₂
424 y⁻¹, about 18% of the passive flux of carbon (Aumont et al., 2018). An additional effect of fishing comes
425 from the disruption and resuspension of sediments by bottom trawling, enhancing remineralization of
426 organic matter and releasing CO₂ in the water column (Atwood et al., 2020). About 1.3% of the global
427 ocean is trawled each year (Sala et al., 2021). If the equivalent of this seabed surface was undisturbed,
428 carbon emissions after 1 year of trawling are estimated at 1.47 Gt aqueous CO₂, equivalent to about 15-
429 20% of the atmospheric CO₂ absorbed by the ocean each year (Sala et al., 2021).

430

431 **2.5 Reducing pollution from excess nutrients (Target 7)**

432

433 Eutrophication, the addition of excess nitrogen and phosphorus or organic matter to aquatic ecosystems,
434 is a major form of inland water and coastal pollution, impacting the climate and the biogeochemical cycles
435 of carbon, nitrogen, phosphorus, sulphide and silica (Rabalais et al., 2014). Eutrophication can result from
436 organic matter loading via sewage discharges or aquaculture, agricultural fertilizer runoff from land, or
437 burning of fossil fuel (Breitburg et al., 2018; Deiningner & Frigstad, 2019). Excess primary and secondary
438 production stimulated by the nutrient input leads to the consumption of oxygen and production of carbon

439 dioxide due to microbial decomposition; this is exacerbated by warming temperatures and enhanced
440 precipitation which may promote stratification and oxygen loss, while amplifying ocean acidification.
441 Eutrophic ocean waters that become hypoxic or suboxic may experience denitrification and ammonium
442 oxidation and release of nitrous oxide (Naqvi et al., 2010), a potent GHG that results in positive climate
443 change feedback. Additionally, under anoxic conditions release of inorganic phosphate and iron from
444 sediments stimulates further primary production and oxygen consumption, as is the case in the oxygen
445 minimum zones off Peru and the Arabian Sea (Linsy et al., 2018; Lomnitz et al., 2016), and toxic hydrogen
446 sulphide may be generated in water or sediments. In anoxic freshwater reservoirs, however, coupling of
447 methanotrophy and denitrification may ameliorate N₂O release (Naqvi et al., 2018). Also, eutrophic
448 freshwater lakes (with > 30 µgTP l⁻¹) bury 5 times more organic carbon than non-eutrophic lakes (Anderson
449 et al., 2014).

450
451 Reduction of low oxygen zones through control of nutrient pollution (oligotrophication) may lead to a
452 significant decrease in deoxygenation and the climate feedbacks associated with N₂O emissions or
453 phosphorus and iron release. Use of wetlands to reduce nitrogen loads through river diversion (Engle,
454 2011) or through new construction (Jahangir et al., 2016) may decrease coastal deoxygenation and
455 associated N₂O or CH₄ emissions. Other benefits of reducing nutrient pollution include likely reduction of
456 harmful algal blooms, which act as co-stressors by releasing toxins and contributing to deoxygenation
457 (Griffith & Gobler, 2019; Pitcher & Jacinto, 2019).

458

459 **2.6 Supporting the productivity, sustainability and resilience of biodiversity in agricultural and** 460 **other managed ecosystems (Target 10)**

461

462 ***Biodiversity-based and biodiversity friendly agricultural systems***

463 Reducing biodiversity loss and enhancing biodiversity in agricultural systems can help mitigate climate
464 change and enhance a wide range of NCPs (Leippert et al., 2020; VanBergen et al., 2020; Wanger et al.,
465 2020). Biodiversity can be promoted in agricultural systems directly – for example, through greater crop
466 diversity, agroforestry or integration of crop production with livestock raising or aquaculture; or indirectly
467 through practices that are biodiversity friendly – for example through organic amendments to soils,
468 reduced tillage or reduced pesticide use (Smith et al. 2020a; Tamburini et al. 2020). In general, these
469 practices do not compromise agricultural yields, and in addition to enhancing biodiversity, they reduce
470 nutrient losses, reduce soil erosion and improve soil fertility (Tamburini et al., 2020). Biodiversity-based
471 and biodiversity friendly agricultural practices also tend to increase carbon sequestration, but have highly
472 variable effects on total GHG emissions, so identifying and implementing win-win practices for biodiversity
473 and climate change mitigation need to be done with this in mind (Smith et al., 2020a; Tamburini et al.,
474 2020). Practices that promote biodiversity in agricultural systems include agroecology (which relies in part

475 on the use of ecological processes to substitute for chemical inputs), regenerative agriculture (which
476 focuses on restoring soil health and reversing biodiversity loss) and organic agriculture, as well as certain
477 aspects of climate-smart agriculture, conservation agriculture, and sustainable intensification (Doré et al.
478 2011; Pretty et al. 2018; FAO 2019a; Giller et al. 2021).

479
480 *In situ* conservation and restoration of biodiversity is one of a suite of practices falling within
481 agroecological principles. Agroecology can also include promoting local and national food production,
482 small-scale farming and local innovations and resource use (Altieri et al., 2012). Mbow et al. (2014) provide
483 an example of African smallholder farmers using agroecological practices (agroforestry) such as
484 diversification of trees on-farm and within the landscape to increase carbon content, prepare for climate
485 extremes at the same time reduce and/or avoid crop failures. In dryland agriculture, soil and water
486 conservation measures potentially improve ground cover and soil carbon content (VanBergen et al., 2020;
487 Wanger et al., 2020) and albedo (Creed et al., 2018).

488
489 The three main objectives of climate-smart agriculture are to sustainably increase agricultural productivity
490 and incomes; adapt to and build resilience to climate change, and reduce GHG emissions (FAO, 2019a).
491 Many of the practices promoted for climate-smart agriculture are also good for biodiversity. For example,
492 the Government of India and its Indian Council of Agricultural Research identified the districts most
493 vulnerable to climate change and implemented climate-smart agricultural interventions such as
494 appropriate use of nitrogen fertilizers, which also reduces negative effects of nitrogen losses on non-
495 agricultural ecosystems, and conservation tillage for increased soil carbon content, which also enhances
496 soil biodiversity. In addition, these measures helped farming groups protect their agricultural systems for
497 local food security and increase adaptive capacity (Rao et al., 2020; Vanbergen et al., 2020) in climate-
498 smart villages (Aggarwal et al. 2018).

499
500 ***Intensive vs less intensive agriculture and the land sharing-land sparing debate***

501 GHG emissions will continue to increase with continued agricultural expansion and continued
502 conventional intensification (Vanbergen et al., 2020). Scenarios that achieve climate change targets
503 generally require substantial changes in agricultural intensification and demand for agricultural products
504 (IPCC, 2019). One approach to conserving biodiversity could be to boost yields per unit area, through
505 sustainable intensification on existing farmland that could in principle spare land for remaining natural
506 habitats (Balmford et al., 2018; Smith et al., 2020a). However, intensive high-yield farming raises other
507 concerns because it can generate high levels of GHG emissions and nutrient losses. For example, excessive
508 fertilization of crops results in N₂O emissions which is a potent GHG, and also results in other gaseous
509 nitrogen losses that contribute to dry and wet deposition of nitrogen into terrestrial ecosystems that can
510 reduce species richness (Galloway et al. 2003; Gerber et al., 2016; Tian et al., 2020). Moreover, NO_x
511 emissions can result in increased tropospheric ozone which can reduce productivity of natural ecosystems

512 (Galloway et al. 2003). In addition, intensive high-yield systems may move the provision of non-material
513 benefits (aesthetics, sense of place etc.) to larger distances from people's centres of livelihood, in contrast
514 to less intensive and often more biodiverse agriculture. Others have argued that the most beneficial
515 approach to conserving biodiversity in agricultural landscapes is to "share" land more effectively with
516 biodiversity, often by reducing agricultural intensity (Kremen, 2015). However, this approach runs the risk
517 of increasing land conversion elsewhere to compensate for reduced agricultural yields per unit area,
518 resulting in an overall negative impact on biodiversity and climate change mitigation (Kremen, 2015;
519 Balmford et al., 2018). A growing consensus is that the benefits and drawbacks of these approaches are
520 highly context dependent, not mutually exclusive and require careful spatial planning (Kremen, 2015;
521 Salles et al., 2017; Egli et al., 2018).

522
523 In terms of demand for agricultural products, Van Meijl et al. (2017) indicate that demand is more
524 influenced by population growth and changes in dietary preferences than for instance by GDP growth.
525 This implies that in the end, agricultural pathway choices are about quality vs. quantity, and that high yield
526 agriculture based on high inputs of energy, fertilizers and pesticides may not be necessary if demand shifts
527 to reduce overconsumption, reduce food waste and loss, and increase the fraction of plant-based foods
528 (Clark et al., 2019).

529

530 ***Using fire and bush removal to combat woody plant encroachment***

531 The process of bush encroachment has been observed on several continents, especially in tropical and
532 subtropical latitudes. Examples include the plains fauna of Africa, with clear direct negative impacts of
533 bush encroachment already visible for vulture, cheetah, and a myriad of smaller grassland bird species. A
534 poorly understood mix of management actions and climate change drivers, including increasing CO₂
535 fertilization of tree growth, is leading to the conversion of formerly open ecosystems to a much more
536 densely tree or bush-covered state (e.g., Stevens et al., 2017). The process occurs in disturbance-driven
537 tropical ecosystems, which generally have much lower standing biomass than is potentially the case in the
538 absence of disturbance (Bond & Midgley, 2012). Wildfire and browsing pressure used to maintain these
539 systems in an "open" condition, and have done so for millennia, resulting in the iconic grassland and
540 savanna landscapes and forest-averse diversity of tropical Africa, South America, and Australasia.

541

542 Experimental efforts using extreme fires and mechanical harvesting have been tested as a way of reversing
543 bush encroachment (e.g., Smit et al., 2016). There are potentially substantive climate change mitigation
544 implications of bush encroachment and its reversal; in Namibia, for example, the extent of bush
545 encroachment is sufficiently large to offset national fossil fuel emissions (Ministry of Environment and
546 Tourism, 2011). Carbon stocks of grassland ecosystems may, however, often be incorrectly discounted in
547 comparison to woody ecosystems (Wigley et al., 2020), due to the failure to account for below ground
548 carbon stocks.

549
550 Maintenance of open ecosystems can, further, help to maintain streamflow (e.g., Creed et al., 2019) and
551 lower intensity of wildfire regimes. Open ecosystems also provide multiple material benefits centred on
552 subsistence livelihoods, including extensive grazing and thatching, as well as the irreplaceable cultural
553 elements associated with these lifestyles. Recognition of the natural cooling effects of high albedo, and
554 the plethora of benefits to people under threat in tropical open ecosystems would provide opportunities
555 for sustainable management of these systems for both local and global benefits. In South Africa, active
556 removal of woody encroachers has created millions of job opportunities, with some demonstrable results
557 with respect to slowing alien plant encroachment (van Wilgen et al., 2012).

558

559 **2.7 Increasing benefits from biodiversity and green/blue spaces in urban areas (Target 12)**

560

561 The United Nations estimated that 55.3% of the world's population lived in urban settlements in 2018
562 (UNDESA, 2019). It is projected that the urbanization trend will continue to accelerate, while the majority
563 of GHG emissions are generated by urban dwellers (United Nations Economist Network, 2020). Contrary
564 to common perception, it has been shown that some cities can harbour rich biodiversity (Secretariat of
565 the Convention on Biological Diversity, 2012; Chan, 2019). Cities can contribute to solutions for both
566 biodiversity loss and climate change and do so in an integrated way. Cities such as Berlin, Edinburgh,
567 Melbourne, Portland, Singapore, Toronto and Washington DC have taken the initiative to adopt
568 biodiversity-friendly, green and sustainable practices (Beatley, 2016; Plastrik & Cleveland, 2018), largely
569 to make them a more liveable and desirable habitat for people.

570

571 Many of the methods used to conserve biodiversity in cities result in the enhancement of sinks for GHGs
572 (Epple et al., 2016). Instead of relying on energy to cool down buildings, designing biodiversity-friendly
573 ('biophilic') buildings and building green infrastructure have gained much traction due to the multiple
574 benefits that have been observed (Enzi et al., 2017). Planting native plants that attract native fauna in
575 vertical greenery and roof-top gardens provide habitats for wildlife as well as reduce ambient
576 temperatures, thereby resulting in decreased energy consumption (Alhashimi et al., 2018; Wong et al.,
577 2003). Other forms of green infrastructures result in multiple benefits such as the emulation of tropical
578 rainforest with multi-tiered and multi-native species planting of roadsides (Chan, 2019), park connectors,
579 the creation of sponge cities (Yu, 2020), the naturalization of drainage channels or the coverage of coastal
580 walls with a range of different materials and forms that increase the establishment of marine biodiversity.
581 All of these measures are implemented to increase biodiversity, with multiple benefits including the
582 reduction in adverse effects of climate change (reduction of urban heat island effect, etc.), the
583 enhancement of regulating (water quality, air quality, soil retention, etc.), material (urban agriculture in
584 roof-top gardens) and non-material ecosystem services connecting people to nature to ensure their
585 physical, psychological and mental well-being (World Health Organization, 2016). The extent to which

586 greening cities also contribute to climate change mitigation has yet to be better quantified, and its
587 potential to be prospected globally.

588

589 **2.8 Mainstreaming biodiversity (Target 14)**

590

591 The Convention on Biological Diversity has put a strong emphasis on the importance of biodiversity
592 mainstreaming which entails “embedding biodiversity considerations into policies, strategies and
593 practices of key public and private actors that impact or rely on biodiversity, so that it is conserved, and
594 sustainably used, both locally and globally” (Huntley & Redford, 2014). As biodiversity conservation and
595 climate change challenges are intricately linked, it follows that biodiversity and climate are most
596 effectively mainstreamed together (Pörtner et al., 2021).

597

598 Several examples illustrate the variety of ways in which biodiversity issues can be mainstreamed, and how
599 this mainstreaming can be beneficial for climate change mitigation. Biodiversity reporting and natural
600 capital accounting can help mainstreaming in governments and policies by informing decision-making. In
601 the case of the System of Environmental Economic Accounting (SEEA) framework, which has been
602 implemented by more than twenty countries, national accounts are used to inform decision-making on
603 biodiversity, climate change mitigation and other environmental issues across government agencies (SCBD
604 2005). Mainstreaming biodiversity in financial instruments, such as fiscal reforms, taxation models and
605 fiscal incentives may also contribute to climate change mitigation. One of the most important and urgent
606 reforms requiring cooperation across many actors are the reduction or elimination of subsidies that are
607 harmful to both biodiversity and climate (see section 2.10 for examples). Better integration of biodiversity
608 into business operations and practices might also benefit climate change mitigation. Businesses are
609 increasingly using GHG emissions accounting to identify and reduce their contributions to climate change,
610 but adoption of biodiversity accounting has lagged behind, in part due to low awareness of biodiversity as
611 a major issue for businesses and to a lack of well-established biodiversity metrics for business to assess
612 and value their impacts and dependencies on biodiversity (Smith et al. 2020b). Climate and biodiversity
613 footprints of businesses are, however, intimately related because reducing biodiversity footprints depends
614 on reducing GHG emissions, since climate change is one of the major factors impacting on biodiversity,
615 and also relies on reducing the impacts of businesses on drivers that are common to both biodiversity loss
616 and climate change such as deforestation, mining and unsustainable agricultural practices (IPBES, 2019).
617 Mainstreaming biodiversity across society, for example through education can be beneficial for climate
618 change especially when they are part of an overall strategy to raise environmental awareness. For
619 example, an examination of educational curricula in 46 countries found that fewer than half of education
620 policies and curricula mentioned climate change and only a fifth made reference to biodiversity, leading
621 to a recommendation that "more emphasis should be given to environmental themes in education, with
622 a particular need to expand integration of climate change and biodiversity" (UNESCO 2021).

623

624 With a growing number of programmes and projects adopting the mainstreaming approach, there are
625 now more case studies documenting their success stories. The Working for Water programme (WfW) in
626 South Africa (Redford et al. 2015) demonstrates that mainstreaming biodiversity resulted in controlling
627 invasive alien species and speeded the rate of legal protection of areas of high biodiversity. In Costa Rica,
628 the joint policies of several Ministries (Environment, Agriculture, Planning and Finance) resulted in a
629 national sustainable development plan that led to the creation of the Forest Incentives Programme where
630 landowners could benefit from income derived from the conservation of forests. This would contribute to
631 climate change mitigation from biodiversity conservation actions. Under the circumstances where climate
632 change mitigation measures could have negative impacts on biodiversity conservation or vice versa, trade-
633 offs should be considered and comprehensively analysed (cf. 3.3).

634

635 **2.9 Eliminating unsustainable consumption patterns (Target 16)**

636

637 Sustainable consumption patterns have clear benefits to biodiversity and ecosystems, and some have links
638 to climate change mitigation. The largest potential for reducing agriculture, forestry and other land use
639 (AFOLU) emissions is through reduced deforestation and forest degradation ($0.4\text{--}5.8\text{ GtCO}_2\text{e y}^{-1}$), a shift
640 towards plant-based diets ($0.7\text{--}8.0\text{ GtCO}_2\text{e y}^{-1}$) and reduced food and agricultural waste ($0.8\text{--}4.5\text{ CO}_2\text{e y}^{-1}$)
641 (Jia et al., 2019). Thus, there is a high potential that consumers' choices can directly impact both
642 biodiversity and the climate. The demand (and the market) for more sustainably harvested and produced
643 wood products can improve forest cover and diversity, with results for both carbon sequestration and
644 albedo (Heilmayr et al., 2020). In addition, changes in demand for other areas of consumption can be
645 more biodiversity- and climate-friendly, for example the demand for different types of electronic goods
646 and appliances, and for clothes that are sustainably produced.

647

648 On the food demand side, nearly 10% of the agricultural land area could be spared globally through halving
649 consumer waste arising from over-consumption in some sectors of society (Alexander et al. 2017). In high-
650 income countries, consumer behaviour significantly influences the amount of food wasted, so raising
651 awareness of the consequences on biodiversity and climate change among consumers, but also along the
652 whole supply chains involving industries and retailers, is of critical importance (FAO, 2019b). Likewise,
653 studies that explore dietary scenarios of reduced consumption of animal protein estimate that between
654 10% and 30% of today's area under agriculture could be freed for other purposes (Alexander et al., 2016;
655 Shin et al., 2019). Improved demand for water wise and biodiversity friendly labelling on foods such as,
656 for example, honey, potatoes, tea, coffee, and other frequently consumed agricultural products is a clear
657 trend in certain markets; and a substantial group of studies are beginning to quantify the benefits to
658 biodiversity and ecosystem services (Ruggeri et al., 2020; Vogt, 2020). Conant et al. (2017) show how the
659 improved management of grazing (e.g., reduced stocking rates and improved rotational strategies, which

660 are often a requirement in the demand for more sustainably produced meat) can lead to an increase in
661 soil carbon stocks - showing rates from 10 to more than 1000 MgC·km⁻²·yr⁻¹.

662

663 **2.10 Eliminating incentives harmful for biodiversity (Target 18)**

664

665 Subsidies are often inefficient, expensive, socially inequitable, and environmentally harmful (OECD, 2005;
666 IPBES, 2019). In 2010, governments agreed to eliminate, phase out or reform subsidies that harm
667 biodiversity by 2020, but biodiversity-harmful subsidies continue. Data on potential impacts of such
668 subsidies on biodiversity is either scant or unavailable (Dempsey et al., 2020). In 2015 alone, OECD
669 countries spent US\$100 billion on agricultural subsidies potentially harmful to nature (OECD, 2019). Global
670 fossil fuel subsidies are at a rate between US\$300 and US\$600 billion per year, resulting in estimated
671 global damage of at least US\$4 trillion in externalities (Coady et al., 2019; Franks et al., 2018).

672

673 The money allocated to promote and conserve biodiversity is outweighed by environmentally harmful
674 subsidies by a factor of ten (OECD, 2019). Thus, the expected positive outcome of subsidies targeted for
675 environmentally beneficial activities are nullified. For example, Brazil spent \$158 million to stop
676 deforestation while it spent \$14 billion (88 times more) subsidizing activities linked to deforestation
677 (McFarland et al., 2015). Similarly, subsidies promoting sustainable fisheries amount to about \$10 billion
678 as compared to \$22 billion in subsidies that promote overfishing (Sumaila et al., 2019). This happens partly
679 due to difficulty in tracking such subsidies, and ignorance of the complexity of institutions. It is also partly
680 due to activities around politicking and interest-group lobbying, e.g., for palm oil in Indonesia (Maxton-
681 Lee, 2018), and petroleum lobbying in Canada (Blue et al., 2018).

682

683 Further, difficulties arise from the effectiveness of environment-friendly subsidies. In Europe, the
684 European Court of Auditors (ECA) found that the foreseen expenditure on 'farmland biodiversity' of the
685 European Commission, amounting to €66 billion between 2014 and 2020, had little effect
686 ([https://www.eca.europa.eu/en/Pages/DocItem.aspx?did={B5A7E9DE-C42E-4C1D-A5D2-
687 03CA1FADE6F8}](https://www.eca.europa.eu/en/Pages/DocItem.aspx?did={B5A7E9DE-C42E-4C1D-A5D2-03CA1FADE6F8})). Over the same period, more than a quarter of the Commissions subsidies under the
688 Common Agricultural Policy had aimed to target climate change mitigation and adaptation, but GHG
689 emissions from European farms are not decreasing
690 ([https://www.eca.europa.eu/en/Pages/DocItem.aspx?did={D6EB02B9-C74E-4017-912B-
691 EE46E75127B1}](https://www.eca.europa.eu/en/Pages/DocItem.aspx?did={D6EB02B9-C74E-4017-912B-EE46E75127B1})). The ECA raises numerous flaws in the ways the subsidies are oriented: the unreliable
692 way the Commission tracks biodiversity expenditure, the low potential of the measures financed, the poor
693 formulation of the agriculture targets, and the poor quality of the indicators used to track progress among
694 the main reasons.

695

696 Halting biodiversity loss in synergy with mitigating climate change can be promoted by fast actions to
697 eliminate harmful subsidies (IPBES, 2019). Actions could include enhancing the subsidy accountability
698 culture among individuals and businesses, the reform of policies for better transparency, reporting and
699 assessments; and the use of policy tools that can provide incentives for maintaining biodiversity, such as
700 public procurement, taxes and fees (Barbier et al., 2018; Barbier et al., 2020; Lundberg & Marklund, 2018;
701 Girardin et al., 2021).
702

703 3. Integrating synergies and trade-offs between multiple goals at the 704 level of landscapes and seascapes

705
706 The success of environmental measures, whether for biodiversity conservation or climate change
707 mitigation, strongly depends on their context in a landscape or seascape, with consideration of the degree
708 of its transformation, its multiple uses, local socio-economic conditions, and the quality of life of local
709 communities. Ecosystem management is thus tasked with achieving multiple goals simultaneously in
710 multifunctional and multiple-use land- and sea-scapes (hereafter referred to as 'scapes). A substantial
711 fraction of net primary productivity and natural resources is appropriated for human use. Results include
712 the spatial fragmentation of 'scapes and a loss of nature, with potential risks of the unrecoverable erosion
713 of natural capital (IPBES, 2018, 2019). Multiple-use 'scapes are the main management context within
714 which synergies and trade-offs between biodiversity conservation and climate change mitigation can be
715 realized (see section 2 in Pörtner et al., 2021). The use and transformation of ecosystems by human society
716 occur mainly at local scales, but these local effects accumulate at larger spatial scales, resulting in
717 significant changes in regional and higher-scale biodiversity and ecosystem functioning. We therefore
718 make use of local case studies (CS) to unpack, amongst other factors, the enabling environments (including
719 incentives and governance factors) that have been effective in fulfilling multiple 'scape objectives
720 simultaneously (Table S3; Figure 1). The selected CS cover a wide range of IPBES units of analyses, and are
721 located on different continents, oceans, and latitudes. They also cover a diversity of conservation
722 measures, types of NCPs, needs of local communities, socio-economic contexts and governance
723 situations. Protection of biodiversity is one of a range of functions fulfilled by a multi-functional and multi-
724 use 'scape. A clear need going forward is to improve our ability to measure real multiple benefits in
725 different contexts (Figure 1), preferably with scope for comparison across cases.
726

Units of Analyses (UoA)

- | | |
|---|---|
| 1 Tropical and subtropical dry and humid forests | 9 Urban and semi urban areas** |
| 2 Temperate and boreal forests and woodlands | 10 Cultivated areas** |
| 3 Mediterranean forests woodlands and scrub | 11 Cryosphere Sea ice maximum extent |
| 4 Tundra and high mountain habitats | 12 Aquaculture areas** |
| 5 Tropical and subtropical savannas and grasslands | 13 Inland surface waters and water bodies |
| 6 Temperate grasslands | 14 Shelf ecosystems |
| 7 Deserts and xeric shrublands | 15/16 Open ocean pelagic systems/Deep sea |
| 8 Wetlands* | 17 Coastal areas intensively used by humans** |

* Spatial representation of wetlands is limited to the tropical and subtropical wetlands
 ** No spatial representation

Impacts of biodiversity measures

CS1	Kailash Sacred Landscape conservation and development initiative	1	7
Maintain/improve/restore forests and rangelands; practice sustainable land use			
	Habitats protected (for snow leopard, musk deer); biodiversity corridors established		
	C sequestered (on forests/rangelands/soils) by adopting ecosystem and farm management practices		
	Water source protected; springs rejuvenated		
	Provision of food, forest products, medicinal plant <i>Ophiocordyceps sinensis</i>		
	Cultural heritage (Mount Kailash and Lake Mansarovar); religious tourism		

CS2	Cultural landscapes in Central Europe	2	10
Simulate traditional land-use systems; avoid succession and intensification			
	Reduced extinction risks of rare and highly adapted species and/or varieties		
	No climax vegetation thus less C sequestered.; CH ₄ emissions by animal husbandry; tradeoffs crop fields vs forests		
	Maintenance of high diversity of pollinators and natural enemies of pest (i.e., biocontrol services)		
	Production of high quality food (meat and vegetarian) but trade-off with food quantity; medicinal plants		
	Maintaining options for adaptation to future changes; cultural: sense of place and mental and physical recreation		

CS3	Irrigated rice terraces and forests in Southeast Asia	1	10
Maintaining forest; avoid application of pesticides			
	Forest as habitat for rare and endangered species; high agrodiversity for stabilization of pest population at low levels		
	C sequestration through maintenance of forests; CH ₄ emissions through paddy fields		
	Water source for irrigation; bicontrol of rice pests		
	Stabilized food supply; avoidance of chemical pollution		
	Sense of place, mental and physical recreation; maintenance of traditional customs including arts; high eco-tourism potential		

CS4	The Coral Triangle initiative	14	
Marine spatial planning, management of fisheries and protection of coastal biodiversity and habitat-forming species (mangroves, coral reefs)			
	Slows biodiversity loss and increases ecological resilience to climate change		
	Improved ecosystem resilience to climate change leads to reduced loss of soils and C (due to deforestation), higher C sinks		
	Improved water quality, soil retention (blue C), coastal protection, habitat complexity, fish nurseries, adaptation to climate change		
	Maintenance of food supply, habitat, livelihoods, firewood, and medicines		
	Maintenance of cultural identity, sense of place, mental and physical recreation, local and international tourism opportunities		

CS5 Biodiversity-friendly cities and urban areas		9
Safeguarding biodiversity and multiple ecosystem service in cities		
	Native ecosystems protected; increased connectivity; habitat restoration; plant diversity of flora	
	Increased C storage and sequestration; regulation C cycling by natural and artificial water bodies	
	Improved water quality, soil retention, coastal protection, habitat complexity, climate change adaptation and mitigation	
	Urban agriculture reduces long-distance transportation that decreases energy consumption/C emission	
	Co-existence with nature essential for physical, psychological, mental well-being; serves educational and recreational functions	

CS6 The Sundarbans India-Bangladesh		1	12
		7	17
Maintaining mangrove forests by implementing protected areas			
	Mangroves are habitat for birds, mammals, reptiles, amphibians, fish including endangered Bengali tiger		
	Gas regulation and C sequestration by mangroves		
	Flood and storm surge regulation by mangroves		
	Provisioning services (e.g., timber, fish) and cultural services (e.g., tourism) are often prioritized over regulating services in the management system for revenue generation, resulting in the steady decline of mangrove forests		

CS7 Southern Ocean South Georgia Island		15
Marine protected area in a pivotal area for megafauna (e.g., baleen whales and albatrosses), control pollution, non-indigenous species and tourism		
	Reduced extinction risk of endangered species	
	C storage increases across trophic levels; efficient seabed sequestration pathways	
	Larger population and fewer stressors so stronger potential for tolerance or adaptation to aspects of climate change	
	Higher productivity potentially benefits regional fisheries	
	Potential for ecotourism, education and understanding of polar issues	

CS8 Marine Biodiversity Beyond National jurisdiction, South Orkney Islands		15	16
Intergovernmental co-operation to protect hotspot of biodiversity and blue carbon			
	Reduced extinction risk for endemic and rare species		
	Enhanced blue C storage pathways to strengthen sequestration		
	Improve climate change tolerance/adaptation; important at physical change hotspot		
	May reduce krill fishery but boosts prey for predators (trade-offs)		
	Strengthen public interest, engagement and ecotourism of remote wildlife, including migratory megafauna		

CS9 Bush encroachment Southern Africa		5	6
		7	
Maintaining appropriate large mammal population with added management of fire regime, using enhanced fire intensity to reverse woody plant dominance in targeted areas			
	Increases the prevalence of high-light, open-ecosystem (grassland) dependent species (i.e., grazers, geophytes)		
	Reduces tree cover but enhances albedo		
	Enhances livelihoods and water quality and quantity, but reduces air quality during burning periods		
	Enhanced food and fiber		
	Maintains traditional livelihoods, cultural practices and sense of place, and nature based tourism		

CS10 Amazonian rainforest		1
Maintain/restore forest areas; improve protected areas management		
	Protect species, ecosystem service and traditional/indigenous communities	
	Conserve/increase C storage in land; control GHG emission by natural and artificial water bodies	
	Critical for water cycle and climate in the continent	
	Provisioning of forest products (i.e. food and medicines); fishing is the main source of protein for locals	
	Indigenous & traditional communities ('seringueiros', 'ribeirinhos') with unique cultural aspects; great potential for ecotourism	

CS11 Pleistocene Park Northeastern Siberia		4
Rewilding the mammoth steppe		
	Restored plant biodiversity and soil of the re-wilded mammoth steppe	
	Attenuates permafrost thawing, increases albedo and C sequestration by soils	
	Soil moisture is reduced in wet moss/shrubby tundra, altered soil provides additional C sequestration	
	Co-benefits that might arise are C-negative wild meat and other C-negative products	
	Provides a year-round base for international research and student mentoring; potential for employment and new tourism economies	

CS12 African peatlands		8
Conserving unique biodiversity of tropical peatland forests		
	Reducing extinction risks of rare and highly adapted species and/or varieties	
	Reduced degradation and loss of land-based C storage; regulate C and water cycling (incl. CH ₄ & CO ₂ emission) by natural peatlands	
	Maintain soils and water quality and water supply	
	Several forest product benefits	
	Preserve cultural identity and livelihoods of local people	

730 *Figure 1. Implementation of biodiversity conservation measures at land- and sea-scape scale.*
731 *Example case studies (full description and references in supplementary material) showing emerging*
732 *synergies or trade-offs between biodiversity conservation, climate change mitigation and nature's*
733 *contributions to people (NCP). For each case study (CS), six pieces of information are provided: the*
734 *biodiversity measure in place, the outcome on biodiversity status, the impacts on climate change*
735 *mitigation, and the impacts on regulating, material and non-material NCPs. On the banner at the*
736 *top of each CS, we provide the corresponding IPBES unit(s) of analysis (on the right) as well as a pie*
737 *chart illustrating the impacts of biodiversity measures (see supporting references in table S2). The*
738 *colour code is as follows: dark green codes for strong beneficial effects, light green for low to*
739 *moderate beneficial effects, orange for unresolved effects or trade-offs. None of the biodiversity*
740 *measures implemented in the CS resulted in negative impacts (coded red), despite the fact that we*
741 *had considered such negative impacts as possible in our assessment. C: carbon, CH₄: methane, pop.:*
742 *population. Map of IPBES Units of analyses can be found at doi:10.5281/zenodo.3975694*

743

744 **3.1. Local to regional actions and the critical role of scale and linkages**

745

746 The use and transformation of ecosystems by human society occurs at local scales, but effects accumulate
747 at larger spatial scales, resulting in significant changes in regional and higher scale biodiversity and
748 ecosystem functioning. In the terrestrial realm, land use and land cover change result from increasing and
749 changing human demands for nature's contributions, with the extent of change varying from place to
750 place, moderated by complex interplay of biophysical, socioeconomic, and governance factors as
751 illustrated by our set of CS (fig. 1 and tables S2-S3). Increasingly, there is recognition that the configuration
752 of these landscapes offers opportunities to achieve multiple objectives relating to both immediate human
753 needs, and long-term sustainability objectives, including those relating to biodiversity and mitigation-
754 related regulating benefits like carbon storage and sequestration. Likewise, achieving multiple objectives
755 at local scales cumulates at the global scale: every local action contributing to climate change mitigation
756 counts.

757

758 Land-use and land cover change for increasing food provision or infrastructure expansion reduce and
759 fragment habitats, and is currently the leading cause of terrestrial biodiversity loss (IPBES, 2018, 2019).
760 These processes also almost always result in net carbon release to the atmosphere (IPCC, 2019), but also
761 provide critical supplies of material benefits that maintain human society and contribute to good quality
762 of life (CS 2, 3, 9, 10, 12). Understanding of how land cover can be allocated between various uses is
763 advancing and providing opportunities to optimize between multiple objectives (CS 2, 3). Such trade-offs
764 may include assessing the balance between production of material NCPs, carbon sequestration via
765 reforestation (regulating NCPs; CS 10) and rewilding (regulating and cultural NCPs; see CS 11 and 2.1 for
766 the beneficial effects of rewilding mammoth steppe with large herbivores in Arctic permafrost areas), and
767 biodiversity.

768

769 Hannah et al. (2020) suggest that at the landscape to national scales, an increase in conserved area from
770 20 to 30% increases the resilience of the conserved area network to climate change (i.e., more species
771 may be assured of persistence). At regional and global scales, the unequal distribution of biodiversity
772 means that some regions have higher concentrations of rare species (Enquist et al., 2019), and, thus,
773 prioritizing conservation objectives in these relatively small regions may permit achievement of species
774 conservation most efficiently (CS 1, 4). Spatial planning methodologies exist that can be applied to
775 maintain ecological functioning even in fragmented landscapes, through the consideration of zonation
776 that leverages landscape heterogeneity across spatial scales (Harlio et al., 2019; Moilanen et al., 2005).
777 Many efforts are undertaken to green cities with multiple co-benefits for human well-being. Such efforts
778 have the potential to connect cities to surrounding natural or managed areas and contribute to both
779 biodiversity conservation and climate change mitigation regionally, as is the case in coastal cities, for
780 example (Beatley, 2014; 2.7 and CS 5).

781
782 In the ocean realm, governance differs greatly from that on land, with very little private ownership, and
783 large amounts of global commons (CS 7, 8). Apart from coastal areas, marine ecosystem transformation
784 occurs mainly via harvesting of consumer species for material benefits, with relatively low rates of plant
785 use, and lower prevalence of high intensity food production systems. Important links between human use
786 of the oceans and climate change mitigation have been identified, with local and regional harvesting
787 scaling up to significantly alter the global food chain, with important impacts on processes like seabed
788 sequestration of carbon and the biological pump of carbon (cf. 2.3, 2.4).

789

790 **3.2. Realizing co-benefits and synergies in land- and sea-scapes**

791

792 At the 'scape level, areas of high species richness (particularly of endemic species) are most often given
793 the highest priority for biodiversity conservation. It happens that many of these same areas also are
794 important carbon sinks (CS 4, 6, 10, 12).

795

796 The Amazon rainforest (CS 10) and mangrove forests (CS 4, 6), in particular, are two biologically diverse
797 iconic ecosystems that are typified by high rates of carbon sequestration (Soares-Filho et al., 2010; Donato
798 et al., 2011; Guannel et al., 2016; Joly et al., 2018). The average annual carbon sequestration rates for
799 mangroves ranges between 600-800 MgCO₂e km⁻² (4 times more than some estimates for tropical forests
800 – Donato et al., 2011 -, but the comparison should not conflate estimates for climax forests, which are
801 approximately carbon-neutral, with early succession forests, which are actively taking up carbon). In the
802 case of mangroves, these rates are thought to be sustained for hundreds of years as sediments build up
803 in the quiet waters of estuaries.

804

805 While high biodiversity areas may also be pronounced in areas of high levels of carbon sequestration
806 (Strassburg et al., 2010), this is not always the case. Coral reefs represent an interesting case, where
807 primary productivity and the build-up of organic carbon over time is low, yet biodiversity is at least an
808 order of magnitude higher than anywhere else in the ocean (Reaka-Kudla, 1997). In this case, coral reefs
809 flourish in oligotrophic waters of tropical coastlines, relying on a low net productivity and nutrient
810 conserving symbiosis with single-celled mutualistic symbionts from the genus *Symbiodinium* (Muscatine
811 & D’Elia, 1978).

812

813 There are also examples of high sequestration- low diversity ecosystems. For example, sequestration of
814 organic carbon in the Southern Ocean is high, where protection safeguards trophic components of carbon
815 pathways (e.g., krill, fish but also benthic communities), so that increased phytoplankton blooms (driven
816 by sea ice losses and glacier retreat) are converted to higher seabed carbon storage, and possibly
817 sequestration (CS 8) in oceans beyond national jurisdiction (Arrigo et al., 2008; Barnes et al., 2016). Yet
818 overall biodiversity can be low compared to non-polar marine ecosystems (Bax et al., 2021). Some caution
819 needs to be exercised, however, given the relatively large proportion of species yet to be discovered in
820 polar and deep-ocean ecosystems which are relatively inaccessible habitats.

821

822 Conservation measures applied to multi-use and multi-functional ‘scapes synergistically contribute to
823 improved human quality of life through the provisioning of context-specific NCPs (most CS). These co-
824 benefits could take the form of material NCPs (food, timber, fuelwood, fodder, medicinal plants) or
825 regulating NCPs (water availability), or cultural/tourism related non-material NCPs (sense of place, cultural
826 or sacred/religious heritage protection, ecotourism) - all these benefits collectively and positively
827 contribute to improved wellbeing of the affected people. Launched in 2010, the Kailash Sacred Landscape
828 Conservation and Development Initiative in India, Nepal and China (CS 1), aimed at conserving threatened
829 species (i.e., snow leopard, musk deer) and their habitats through reforestation, rangeland and farmland
830 management following ecosystem-based management approaches. This programme has great potential
831 to generate climate change mitigation and adaptation co-benefits through carbon storage and
832 sequestration in trees, rangelands and soils (Aryal et al., 2018; Joshi et al., 2019; Liniger et al., 2020; Uddin
833 et al., 2015). In addition, the Kailash Sacred Landscape has benefited local and distant users through a
834 range of NCPs, such as timber, fodder, fuel wood, medicinal plants, water source protection and
835 rejuvenation of springs (Badola et al., 2017; Chaudhary et al., 2020; Liniger et al., 2020; Nepal et al., 2018;
836 Tewari et al., 2020; Thapa et al., 2018), protection of sacred cultural and religious sites – Kailash Mountain
837 and Mansarovar – and the promotion of eco-tourism (Adler et al., 2013; Pandey et al., 2016). Kailash
838 Sacred Landscape also benefits distant downstream users of India, Nepal, and China through the
839 (continued) provision of flowing waters for irrigation and other purposes (including hydro-power
840 generation) by protecting the sources.

841

842 Other such co-benefits have been reported in various 'scapes throughout the world. For example, about
843 7.2 million people of India and Bangladesh, half of them are considered poor, rely on Sundarbans (CS 6)
844 for multiple contributions from nature (carbon sequestration, gas regulation, disturbance regulation)
845 (IUCN, 2017, 2020). Similarly, co-benefits of conservation measures have been demonstrated in cities
846 (e.g., Beatley, 2016) which typically concentrate multi-uses and multi-functional spaces crossed by islands
847 of biodiversity (cf. 2.7 and CS 5). The Coral Triangle Initiative (CS 4) generates multiple benefits from
848 nature of local to regional significance (Friess et al., 2020), such as improvements to coastal water quality,
849 nursery areas for fish, coastal protection, and maintenance of food, livelihoods, and cultural significance.
850 Similarly, conservation of African peatlands yields high value water services to local people (CS 12). Not
851 all of these benefits are equally prioritized due to the strong dependence of the livelihoods and income
852 of poor people on material (fish, timber) and non-material (tourism) contributions from nature (CS 1, 3,
853 4; Uddin et al., 2013).

854
855 The success of conservation measures in multi-use and multi-functional land- and sea-scapes is sensitive
856 to operational issues and governance challenges. In Amazon rainforests (CS 10), the global scale carbon
857 sink function is being negatively impacted by deforestation and expansion of cattle and soybean
858 production (Malhi et al., 2008), mining activities (Rosa et al., 2018), and construction of big dams
859 (Fearnside, 2016). Similarly, in Pleistocene Park, CH₄ released by large animals could negatively affect the
860 carbon cycle, and reduction of shrub cover and leaf area decreases CO₂ uptake (Falk et al., 2015; Schmitz
861 et al., 2018)(CS 11). In Africa, the reforestation of dryland ecosystems (grasslands, savannah, forests) by
862 exotic species (*Acacia* spp.) has created bush encroachment/invasion, impacting biodiversity negatively
863 and supply of nature's contributions to local people (fuelwood, fodder, water availability), affecting their
864 livelihoods and wellbeing (CS 9). Lack of strong policy and operational coherences between countries
865 could lead to suboptimal outcomes of the conservation measures (cf. 3.3).

866
867 Biodiversity conservation successes to generate co-benefits, specifically climate change mitigation or
868 adaptation, depend on consideration of values held by the key stakeholders, primarily the indigenous and
869 local people, in conservation and management initiatives. Values reflect behaviour. Environmental
870 interventions aimed to change human behaviour should thus be rooted in values held by concerned
871 groups of people. Among the case studies examined, differing values are held by different groups of
872 people in conserving or managing the 'scapes. Examples include: cultural values attached to sacred places
873 in the Kailash Sacred Landscape (CS 1), strong dependency of indigenous people on forest resources for
874 livelihoods and traditional significance in Amazon (CS 10), local people/fishermen and their dependency
875 on material benefits from nature (fishing) in the Coral Triangle (CS 4) and the Sundarbans (CS 6), and
876 strong and traditional livelihood linkages of local people with the dryland ecosystems in Africa (CS 9).

877

878 3.3. Evaluating trade-offs

879
880 There are conservation measures and traditional land- and sea- uses that contribute to biodiversity
881 conservation, but have trade-offs with climate change mitigation. In South Africa, wildfire management
882 to limit bush encroachment contributes to maintaining species diversity in open ecosystems (CS 9). These
883 measures to maintain open ecosystems contribute to cooling effects (by high albedo land surface) and
884 biodiversity, as well as providing multiple material NCPs centred on subsistence livelihoods, including
885 extensive grazing and thatching, and the irreplaceable cultural elements associated with these lifestyles
886 (e.g., Creed et al., 2019). However, they would not result in apparent carbon storage and sequestration
887 that can be obtained through large-scale afforestation as measured by standard accounting for above
888 ground stocks, which ignores the potentially large below-ground stocks of grassland ecosystems (Wigley
889 et al., 2020). Further, the grazing of cattle, sheep, and goats in European landscapes contributes to shaping
890 traditional cultural landscapes, and providing food (e.g., meat, milk, cheese), pollination for agricultural
891 production nearby contributing to livelihood of locals. However, methane emissions from rumination by
892 livestock is a known source of climate change (IPCC, 2019) (CS 2). Similarly, rice cultivation in the sloping
893 terraced rice fields of Southeast Asia contributes to food production, water flow regulation, sediment
894 regulation along with traditional cultural landscapes (CS 3), but, on the other hand, rice paddies are known
895 sources of methane emissions (Saunois et al., 2016; Zhang et al., 2020).

896
897 Trade-offs in NCPs have spatially differentiated consequences for their different beneficiaries. Providers
898 and beneficiaries of NCP are often different, and their relationships vary according to the type of NCP
899 (Fisher et al., 2009). In Sundarbans (CS 6), for instance, mangrove forests provide carbon storage and
900 sequestration contributing to global climate change mitigation whose beneficiaries spread across the
901 world (Sannigrahi et al., 2020a; 2020b) while the other mangrove regulating services such as water and
902 sediment retention and disturbance regulations (e.g., against cyclones and storm surges) are appreciated
903 mostly by locals (IUCN, 2020; Sannigrahi et al., 2020a). Fish and shrimps nurtured through aquaculture
904 relying on nutrient cycling of mangrove areas are often delivered to consumers in remote areas mediated
905 by supply chains while some firewood and timber forest products are consumed locally for sustenance of
906 locals (IUCN, 2020). The non-material benefits of forests, such as recreation and tourism are appreciated
907 not only by locals but also by visitors who travel to the mangroves. In this way, stakeholders of the societal
908 contributions of mangroves are diverse, and the use of one of such contributions (e.g. shrimp aquaculture)
909 will affect the state of other contributions (e.g., carbon storage and water quality regulation) through the
910 alteration of the mangrove forest.

911
912 In Sundarbans, although climate and disturbance regulations, and habitat provisions are often evaluated
913 to be the vital NCP (Sannigrahi et al., 2020a, 2020b), local stakeholders including governments prioritize
914 the production and use of NCP that lead to their economic benefits such as food and tourism, which results

915 in the decline in mangrove's capacity in climate change mitigation (Uddin et al., 2013). Similar challenge
916 was found in the areas managed by the Kailash Sacred Landscape Conservation and Development
917 Initiative (CS 1), as the growing trend of tourism activities often increase waste generation, energy
918 consumption and enhance forest degradation, which is a trade-off with climate change mitigation (Nepal
919 et al., 2018; Pandey et al., 2016) . This contrasts with consideration of climate change adaptation which
920 has direct implications for local communities.

921
922 Biodiversity conservation measures will have unintended consequences and challenges which need to be
923 recognised, rectified and addressed through proper planning and governance mechanisms. This could be
924 done through a holistic, integrated, consultative, and adaptive approach within and across nations. Cross-
925 border cooperation helps countries manage trade-offs among multiple NCPs, while conserving
926 biodiversity synergistically for climate change mitigation or adaptation. For instance, the Coral Triangle
927 Initiative (CS 4), focused on the conservation of the Coral Triangle between Pacific and Indian Ocean, is
928 participated by six countries (i.e., Indonesia, Malaysia, Papua New Guinea, Philippines, Solomon Islands
929 and Timor-Leste) (Weeks et al., 2014). The countries have worked jointly on the designation of priority
930 seascapes, conservation planning, marine protected area networks (Asaad et al., 2018), aiming to balance
931 the biodiversity conservation and socioeconomic development of the region while coping with climate
932 change mitigation through the regeneration and restoration of coastal mangrove forests. Similarly, the
933 Kailash Sacred Landscape Conservation and Development Initiative (CS 1) established by Nepal, India, and
934 China for the conservation of biodiversity, NCP and cultural heritage of the pilgrimage to Mount Kailash,
935 has contributed to establishing biodiversity corridors connecting protected areas located in three
936 countries, adaptive ecosystem management, and improved livelihoods of local people (Zomer & Oli,
937 2011). For transboundary initiatives, the agreement of the countries concerned is essential. This is
938 especially challenging in establishing protected areas on the high seas, which requires the agreement of
939 member states under a multilateral environmental instrument to protect biodiversity, which is currently
940 under negotiation by the UN (Tessnow-von Wysocki and Vadrot, 2020). The South Orkney Islands
941 Southern Shelf Marine Protected Area (CS 8) is a good example of a successful transboundary initiative,
942 contributing also to climate change mitigation with its high carbon storage and sequestration capacity
943 (Barnes et al., 2016; Trathan et al., 2014).

944 4. Conclusion

945
946 Ecosystems and their component species play a central role in the climate system, due to their effects on
947 the surface energy balance, water balance, consumption, and production of radiatively active gases and
948 aerosols. Conservation actions motivated by biodiversity concerns have traditionally not focused on this
949 central role, but its recent recognition demands an assessment of how conservation actions can best be
950 aligned with climate goals, and where this alignment may be less feasible, irrelevant, or conflictual.

951

952 We find that many instances of conservation actions intended to halt, slow or reverse biodiversity loss
953 can simultaneously slow anthropogenic climate change significantly. Specifically, we identified direct co-
954 benefits in 14 out of the 21 action targets of the post-2020 global biodiversity framework of the CBD,
955 notwithstanding the indirect links that can as well support both biodiversity conservation and climate
956 change mitigation. The conservation actions with the largest potential for mitigating climate change
957 include avoided deforestation and ecosystem restoration (especially of high-carbon ecosystems such as
958 forests, mangroves, or seagrass meadows). The evidence suggests that conservation actions have, on
959 balance, more mutually synergistic benefits than antagonistic trade-offs with respect to contributions
960 regulating the climate system. Synergies between biodiversity, climate change mitigation, other NCPs and
961 good quality of life are seldom fully quantified and integrated, and the evidence base for assessing these
962 could be strengthened if this were done more routinely. We suggest that the development of integrated
963 indicators, models and scenarios would facilitate decision-making for mainstreaming and applying
964 ecosystem-based integrative approaches that include biodiversity benefits.

965

966 Locally motivated biodiversity conservation actions can be incentivized, guided and prioritized by global
967 objectives and targets, including climate benefits, but there are risks of overly simplified messages that
968 assume positive synergies, such as unquestioning support for tree-planting campaigns regardless of local
969 context. However, local initiatives matter since the benefits of many small and local biodiversity measures
970 accumulate at the global level, towards climate change mitigation, while also providing multiple local
971 benefits. For example, nature-based solutions in urban contexts can individually make a small contribution
972 to global climate change mitigation and biodiversity protection, but provide quality of life benefits locally
973 to a large share of the world population.

974

975 At the landscape or seascape level, areas of high biodiversity are prioritized for biodiversity conservation
976 measures, and many of these same areas have high rates of carbon sequestration. However, there are
977 important exceptions to the generally positive synergy between conservation and climate change
978 mitigation. For example, disturbance management, such as through reducing wildfire frequency, has been
979 shown to reduce biodiversity substantially due to the dependence of many wild species on disturbance
980 regimes. The reintroduction of key animal species in rewilding efforts may also reduce standing carbon
981 stocks through enhancing the disturbance regime. In some subtropical regions of the world where woody
982 plant cover is increasing due to climate and CO₂ drivers, the use of enhanced disturbance regimes to
983 control tree and shrub encroachment is conflictual with mitigation goals but may conserve biodiversity
984 and enhance critical ecosystem services, such as water yield from catchments.

985

986 The implementation of appropriate mixed-use land- and sea-scapes through a holistic, integrated,
987 consultative, and adaptive approach has the potential to enhance co-benefits between conserving

988 biodiversity, mitigating climate change, and enhancing good quality of life. However, the realization of
989 synergistic benefits are strongly dependent on which biomes, ecosystem uses, and sectoral interactions
990 are under consideration. It may be impossible to achieve win-win synergies, or even manage the trade-
991 offs between climate and biodiversity in every single patch of a landscape, but achieving sustainable
992 outcomes becomes progressively easier at the scape level. Therefore, local to global policies and practices
993 designed for biodiversity conservation or climate change mitigation should be considered in an integrated
994 way so that win-win synergies and NCPs can be maximised.
995

996 Acknowledgements

997
998 This paper is based on the work and findings from the IPBES-IPCC co-sponsored workshop on Biodiversity
999 and Climate Change that was held in December 2020. The views expressed here, however, represent the
1000 individual views of the authors. We are grateful to the scientific steering committee of the IPBES-IPCC
1001 workshop, review editors, the IPBES and IPCC Secretariat and Technical Support Units. We are especially
1002 grateful to Anne Larigauderie for her vision and continued support on all fronts, Yuka Estrada for having
1003 drawn the central figure of the paper, and Sally Archibald, Debora Ley, Unai Pascual, and Valérie Masson-
1004 Delmotte for their critical advice on previous versions of the manuscript.

1005 YJS acknowledges support from the Biodiversa and Belmont Forum project SOMBEE (BiodivScen ERA-Net
1006 COFUND programme, ANR contract n°ANR-18-EBI4-0003-01), and the European Union's Horizon 2020
1007 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869300 (FutureMARES). GI was
1008 supported by the project #0148-2019-0007 of the Institute of Geography, Russian Academy of Sciences.
1009 ADR acknowledges the support of REVOcean during this work. SH was supported by the Research Institute
1010 for Humanity and Nature Project No. 14200103, the Environment Research and Technology Development
1011 Fund (S-15) of the Ministry of the Environment, Japan, and CRRP2018-03MY-Hashimoto by the Asia-Pacific
1012 Network for Global Change Research.

1013

1014 Author contribution

1015 Y.J.S., G.F.M., H.T.N., S.H., R.P., O.H.G., J.S., L.C., G.I., E.A. conceived the initial ideas of the paper, and all
1016 authors reviewed the literature and wrote the manuscript.

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1018 References

- 1019 Adhikari S., Bajracharaya S. (2009). A review of carbon dynamics and sequestration in wetlands. *Journal of Wetlands*
1020 *Ecology* 2, 2–46. <https://doi.org/10.3126/jowe.v2i1.1855>
- 1021 Adler C. E., McEvoy D., Chhetri P., & Kruk E. (2013). The role of tourism in a changing climate for conservation and
1022 development. A problem-oriented study in the Kailash Sacred Landscape, Nepal. *Policy Sciences*, 46(2), 161–
1023 178. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11077-012-9168-4>
- 1024 Agarwala M., Atkinson G., Baldock C. & Gardiner B. (2014). Natural capital accounting and climate change. *Nature*
1025 *Climate Change*, 4(7), 520–522. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate2257>
- 1026 Aggarwal P. K., Jarvis A. J., Campbell B. M., Zougmore R., Khatri-Chhetri, A., Vermeulen S. J., Loboguerrero A. M.,
1027 Sebastian L., Kinyangi J., Bonilla-Findji O., Radeny M., Recha J., Martinez-Baron D., Huyer S., Thornton P. K.,
1028 Wollenberg L., and Hansen J. (2018). The climate-smart village approach: framework of an integrative strategy
1029 for scaling up adaptation options in agriculture. *Ecol. Soc.*, 23 (1) p. 14
1030 <https://www.ecologyandsociety.org/vol23/iss1/art14/>
- 1031 Ahlström, A., et al. (2015). The dominant role of semi-arid ecosystems in the trend and variability of the land CO₂
1032 sink. *Science* 348 (6237): 895-899. doi: 10.1126/science.aaa1668
- 1033 Albrecht, M., Kleijn, D., Williams, N. M., Tschumi, M., Blaauw, B. R., Bommarco, R., Campbell, A. J., Dainese, M.,
1034 Drummond, F. A., Entling, M. H., Ganser, D., Arjen de Groot, G., Goulson, D., Grab, H., Hamilton, H., Herzog,
1035 F., Isaacs, R., Jacot, K., Jeanneret, P., ... Sutter, L. (2020). The effectiveness of flower strips and hedgerows on
1036 pest control, pollination services and crop yield: A quantitative synthesis. *Ecology Letters*, 23(10), 1488–1498.
1037 <https://doi.org/10.1111/ele.13576>
- 1038 Alexander, P., et al. (2016). Human appropriation of land for food: The role of diet. *Global Environmental Change-*
1039 *Human and Policy Dimensions* 41: 88-98. doi:10.1016/J.GLOENVCHA.2016.09.005
- 1040 Alexander, P., Brown, C., Arneith, A., Finnigan, J., Moran, D., & Rounsevell, M. (2017). Losses, inefficiencies and waste
1041 in the global food system. *Agricultural Systems*, 153, 190–200. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2017.01.014>
- 1042 Alhashimi, L., Aljawi, L., Gashgari, R., & Almoudi, A. (2018). The Effect of Rooftop Garden on Reducing the Internal
1043 Temperature of the Rooms in Buildings. *Proceedings of the 4th World Congress on Mechanical, Chemical, and*
1044 *Material Engineering (MCM'18) Madrid, Spain - August 16-18, 2018.* <https://doi.org/10.11159/icmie18.114>
- 1045 Altieri, M.A., Funes-Monzote, F.R. & Petersen, P. (2012). Agroecologically efficient agricultural systems for
1046 smallholder farmers: contributions to food sovereignty. *Agron. Sustain. Dev.* 32, 1–13.
1047 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13593-011-0065-6>
- 1048 Anadón, J. D., Sala, O. E., Turner, B. L., & Bennett, E. M. (2014). Effect of woody-plant encroachment on livestock
1049 production in North and South America. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 111(35), 12948–
1050 12953. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1320585111>
- 1051 Anderson, N. J., Bennion, H., & Lotter, A. F. (2014). Lake eutrophication and its implications for organic carbon
1052 sequestration in Europe. *Global Change Biology*, 20(9), 2741–2751. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.12584>
- 1053 Anisha, N.F., Mauroner, A., Lovett, G., Neher, A., Servos, M., Minayeva, T., Schutten, H., & Minelli, L. (2020). Locking
1054 Carbon in Wetlands: Enhancing Climate Action by Including Wetlands in NDCs.
- 1055 Ariunbaatar, A., & et al. (2017). Strategic Planning for Peatlands in Mongolia (Assessment Report TA-8802; Technical
1056 Assistance, p. 273). Asian Development Bank.
- 1057 Arneith, A., et al. (2010). Terrestrial biogeochemical feedbacks in the climate system. *Nature Geoscience* 3(8): 525-
1058 532. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ngeo905>
- 1059 Arrigo, K. R., van Dijken, G. L., & Bushinsky, S. (2008). Primary production in the Southern Ocean, 1997–2006. *Journal*
1060 *of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 113(C8), C08004. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2007JC004551>

1061 Aryal, J.P. et al. (2016). Conservation agriculture-based wheat production better copes with extreme climate events
1062 than conventional tillage-based systems: A case of untimely excess rainfall in Haryana, India. *Agric. Ecosyst.*
1063 *Environ.*, 233, 325–335, doi:10.1016/j.agee.2016.09.013.

1064 Aryal, K., Poudel, S., Chaudary, R. P., Chettri, N., Ning, W., Shaoliang, Y., & Kotru, R. (2018). Conservation and
1065 management practices of traditional crop genetic diversity by the farmers: A case from Kailash Sacred
1066 Landscape, Nepal. *Journal of Agriculture and Environment*, 18, 15–28.
1067 <https://doi.org/10.3126/aej.v18i0.19886>

1068 Asaad, I., Lundquist, C. J., Erdmann, M. V., Van Hooi donk, R., & Costello, M. J. (2018). Designating spatial priorities
1069 for marine biodiversity conservation in the Coral Triangle. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 5, 400.
1070 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2018.00400>

1071 Atwood, T. B., Connolly, R. M., Ritchie, E. G., Lovelock, C. E., Heithaus, M. R., Hays, G. C., Fourqurean, J. W., &
1072 Macreadie, P. I. (2015). Predators help protect carbon stocks in blue carbon ecosystems. *Nature Climate*
1073 *Change*, 5(12), 1038–1045. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate2763>

1074 Atwood, T. B., Witt, A., Mayorga, J., Hammill, E., & Sala, E. (2020). Global Patterns in Marine Sediment Carbon Stocks.
1075 *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 7, 165. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2020.00165>

1076 Aumont, O., Maury, O., Lefort, S., & Bopp, L. (2018). Evaluating the Potential Impacts of the Diurnal Vertical Migration
1077 by Marine Organisms on Marine Biogeochemistry. *Global Biogeochemical Cycles*, 32(11), 1622–1643.
1078 <https://doi.org/10.1029/2018GB005886>

1079 Avagyan, A., & et al. (2017). Smoke on Water – Countering Global Threats From Peatland Loss and Degradation. A
1080 UNEP Rapid Response Assessment. (p. 70) [A RAPID RESPONSE ASSESSMENT,]. United Nations Environment
1081 Programme and GRID-Arendal. <https://www.grida.no/publications/355>

1082 Babcock, R. C., Bustamante, R. H., Fulton, E. A., Fulton, D. J., Haywood, M. D., Hobday, A. J., Kenyon, R., Matear, R.
1083 J., Plagányi, E. E., & Richardson, A. J. (2019). Severe continental-scale impacts of climate change are happening
1084 now: Extreme climate events impact marine habitat forming communities along 45% of Australia’s coast.
1085 *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 6, 411. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2019.00411>

1086 Baccini, A., Walker, W., Carvalho, L., Farina, M., Sulla-Menashe, D. and Houghton, R.A. (2017) Tropical forests are a
1087 net carbon source based on aboveground measurements of gain and loss. *Science* 358: 230-233. DOI:
1088 10.1126/science.aam5962

1089 Badola, E., Rawal, R., & Dhyani, P. (2017). Stories of Success: Narratives from a sacred land. GBPIHED, Almora,
1090 Uttarakhand (India).

1091 Bajželj, B., Richards, K. S., Allwood, J. M., Smith, P., Dennis, J. S., Curmi, E., & Gilligan, C. A. (2014). Importance of
1092 food-demand management for climate mitigation. *Nature Climate Change*, 4(10), 924–929.
1093 <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate2353>

1094 Baldi, G., & Jobbágy, E. G. (2012). Land use in the dry subtropics: Vegetation composition and production across
1095 contrasting human contexts. *Journal of Arid Environments*, 76, 115–127.
1096 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaridenv.2011.08.016>

1097 Baldi, Germán, Verón, S. R., & Jobbágy, E. G. (2013). The imprint of humans on landscape patterns and vegetation
1098 functioning in the dry subtropics. *Global Change Biology*, 19(2), 441–458. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.12060>

1099 Balmford, Andrew, Amano, T., Bartlett, H., Chadwick, D., Collins, A., Edwards, D., Field, R., Garnsworthy, P., Green,
1100 R., Smith, P., Waters, H., Whitmore, A., Broom, D. M., Chara, J., Finch, T., Garnett, E., Gathorne-Hardy, A.,
1101 Hernandez-Medrano, J., Herrero, M., ... Eisner, R. (2018). The environmental costs and benefits of high-yield
1102 farming. *Nature Sustainability*, 1(9), 477–485. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-018-0138-5>

1103 Barbier, E. B., Lozano, R., Rodríguez, C. M., & Troëng, S. (2020). Adopt a carbon tax to protect tropical forests. *Nature*,
1104 578(7794), 213–216. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-020-00324-w>

- 1105 Barbier, E., Burgess, J., & Dean, T. (2018). How to pay for saving biodiversity. *Science*, 360, 486–488.
1106 <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aar3454>
- 1107 Barnes, D. K. A., Fleming, A., Sands, C. J., Quartino, M. L., & Deregibus, D. (2018). Icebergs, sea ice, blue carbon and
1108 Antarctic climate feedbacks. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and
1109 Engineering Sciences*, 376(2122), 20170176. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2017.0176>
- 1110 Barnes, D. K. A., Ireland, L., Hogg, O. T., Morley, S., Enderlein, P., & Sands, C. J. (2016). Why is the South Orkney Island
1111 shelf (the world's first high seas marine protected area) a carbon immobilization hotspot? *Global Change
1112 Biology*, 22(3), 1110–1120. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.13157>
- 1113 Bar-On, Y. M., Phillips, R., & Milo, R. (2018). The biomass distribution on Earth. *Proceedings of the National Academy
1114 of Sciences*, 115(25), 6506–6511. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1711842115>
- 1115 Barragán, J. M., & de Andrés, M. (2015). Analysis and trends of the world's coastal cities and agglomerations. *Ocean
1116 & Coastal Management*, 114, 11–20. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2015.06.004>
- 1117 Bax, N., Sands, C. J., Gogarty, B., Downey, R. V., Moreau, C. V. E., Moreno, B., Held, C., Paulsen, M. L., McGee, J.,
1118 Haward, M., & Barnes, D. K. A. (2021). Perspective: Increasing blue carbon around Antarctica is an ecosystem
1119 service of considerable societal and economic value worth protecting. *Global Change Biology*, 27(1), 5–12.
1120 <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.15392>
- 1121 Bayraktarov, E., Saunders, M. I., Abdullah, S., Mills, M., Beher, J., Possingham, H. P., Mumby, P. J., & Lovelock, C. E.
1122 (2016). The cost and feasibility of marine coastal restoration. *Ecological Applications*, 26(4), 1055–1074.
1123 <https://doi.org/10.1890/15-1077>
- 1124 Beatley, T. (2014). *Blue Urbanism: Exploring Connections between Cities and Oceans*. Island Press.
- 1125 Beatley, T. (2016). *Handbook of Biophilic City Planning and Design*. Island Press.
- 1126 Belcher, A., Henson, S. A., Manno, C., Hill, S. L., Atkinson, A., Thorpe, S. E., Fretwell, P., Ireland, L., & Tarling, G. A.
1127 (2019). Krill faecal pellets drive hidden pulses of particulate organic carbon in the marginal ice zone. *Nature
1128 Communications*, 10(1), 889. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-08847-1>
- 1129 Blue, G., Daub, S., Yunker, Z., & Rajewicz, L. (2018). In the Corporate Interest: Fossil Fuel Industry Input into Alberta
1130 and British Columbia's Climate Leadership Plans. *Canadian Journal of Communication*, 43(1).
1131 <https://doi.org/10.22230/cjc.2018v43n1a3309>
- 1132 Bond, W. J., & Midgley, G. F. (2012). Carbon dioxide and the uneasy interactions of trees and savannah grasses.
1133 *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 367(1588), 601–612.
1134 <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2011.0182>
- 1135 Breitburg, D., Levin, L. A., Oschlies, A., Grégoire, M., Chavez, F. P., Conley, D. J., Garçon, V., Gilbert, D., Gutiérrez, D.,
1136 Isensee, K., Jacinto, G. S., Limburg, K. E., Montes, I., Naqvi, S. W. A., Pitcher, G. C., Rabalais, N. N., Roman, M.
1137 R., Rose, K. A., Seibel, B. A., ... Zhang, J. (2018). Declining oxygen in the global ocean and coastal waters.
1138 *Science*, 359(6371), eaam7240. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aam7240>
- 1139 Bull, Joseph William, & Strange, N. (2018). The global extent of biodiversity offset implementation under no net loss
1140 policies. *Nature Sustainability*, 1(12), 790–798. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-018-0176-z>
- 1141 Bullock, E. L., Woodcock, C. E., Souza, C., & Olofsson, P. (2020). Satellite-based estimates reveal widespread forest
1142 degradation in the Amazon. *Global Change Biology*, 26(5), 2956–2969. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.15029>
- 1143 Butchart, S. H. M., Miloslavich, P., Reyers, B., Subramanian, S. M., Adams, C., Bennett, E., Czucz, B., Galetto, L., Galvin,
1144 K., Reyes-Garcia, V., Gerber, L. R., Bekele, T., Jetz, W., Kosamu, I. B. M., Palomo, M. G., Panahi, M., Selig, E. R.,
1145 Singh, G. S., Tarkhnishvili, D., Xu, H., Lynch, A. J., Mwampamba, T. H., Samakov, A. (2019). Chapter 3. Assessing
1146 progress towards meeting major international objectives related to nature and nature's contributions to
1147 people. In: *Global assessment report of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and
1148 Ecosystem Services*. Brondizio, E. S., Settele, J., Diaz, S., Ngo, H. T. (eds). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany.
1149 214 pages DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3832053

- 1150 Cahoon, S. M. P., Sullivan, P. F., Post, E., & Welker, J. M. (2012). Large herbivores limit CO₂ uptake and suppress
1151 carbon cycle responses to warming in West Greenland. *Global Change Biology*, 18(2), 469–479.
1152 <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2011.02528.x>
- 1153 CBD. (2021). First draft of the post-2020 global biodiversity framework (CBD/WG2020/3/3). Convention on Biological
1154 Diversity. <https://www.cbd.int/conferences/post2020/wg2020-03/documents>
- 1155 Chan L. (2019). Chapter 5: Nature in the city. *In* Planning Singapore: The Experimental City. Eds: Stephen Hamnet &
1156 Belinda Yuen. Routledge. London. (pp. 109–129).
- 1157 Chappell, A., Baldock, J., & Sanderman, J. (2016). The global significance of omitting soil erosion from soil organic
1158 carbon cycling schemes. *Nature Climate Change*, 6(2), 187–191. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate2829>
- 1159 Chappell, A., Webb, N. P., Leys, J. F., Waters, C. M., Orgill, S., & Eyres, M. J. (2019). Minimising soil organic carbon
1160 erosion by wind is critical for land degradation neutrality. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 93, 43–52.
1161 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2018.12.020>
- 1162 Chaudhary, N., Miller, P. A., & Smith, B. (2017). Modelling Holocene peatland dynamics with an individual-based
1163 dynamic vegetation model. *Biogeosciences*, 14(10), 2571–2596. <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-14-2571-2017>
- 1164 Chaudhary, A., Sarkar, M. S., Adhikari, B. S., & Rawat, G. S. (2020). *Ageratina adenophora* and *Lantana camara* in
1165 Kailash Sacred Landscape, India: Current distribution and future climatic scenarios through modeling. *BioRxiv*,
1166 2020.09.14.295899. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.09.14.295899>
- 1167 Ciais, P., C. Sabine, G. Bala, L. Bopp, V. Brovkin, J. Canadell, A. Chhabra, R. DeFries, J. Galloway, M. Heimann, C. Jones,
1168 C. Le Quéré, R.B. Myneni, S. Piao, & P. Thornton. (2013). Carbon and Other Biogeochemical Cycles. *In* Climate
1169 Change 2013: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Fifth Assessment Report of
1170 the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (Stocker, T.F., D. Qin, G.-K. Plattner, M. Tignor, S.K. Allen, J.
1171 Boschung, A. Nauels, Y. Xia, V. Bex and P.M. Midgley (eds.)), pp. 465–570). Cambridge University Press.
- 1172 Clark M. A., Springmann M., Hill J. and Tilman D. (2019). Multiple health and environmental impacts of foods *Proc.*
1173 *Natl. Acad. Sci.* 116 23357–62. doi: 10.1073/pnas.1906908116
- 1174 Coady, D., Parry, I., Le, N.-P., & Shang, B. (2019). Global fossil fuel subsidies remain large: An update based on
1175 country-level estimates. *IMF Working Papers*, 19(89), 39. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5089/9781484393178.001>
- 1176 Conant, R. T., Cerri, C. E. P., Osborne, B. B., & Paustian, K. (2017). Grassland management impacts on soil carbon
1177 stocks: A new synthesis. *Ecological Applications*, 27(2), 662–668. <https://doi.org/10.1002/eap.1473>
- 1178 Couwenberg, J., Dommain, R., & Joosten, H. (2009). Greenhouse gas fluxes from tropical peatlands in south-east
1179 Asia: GREENHOUSE GAS FLUXES FROM TROPICAL PEATLANDS. *Global Change Biology*, 16(6), 1715–1732.
1180 <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2009.02016.x>
- 1181 Creed, I. F., Jones, J. A., Archer, E., Claassen, M., Ellison, D., McNulty, S. G., van Noordwijk, M., Vira, B., Wei, X.,
1182 Bishop, K., Blanco, J. A., Gush, M., Gyawali, D., Jobbágy, E., Lara, A., Little, C., Martin-Ortega, J., Mukherji, A.,
1183 Murdiyarso, D., ... Xu, J. (2019). Managing Forests for Both Downstream and Downwind Water. *Frontiers in*
1184 *Forests and Global Change*, 2. <https://doi.org/10.3389/ffgc.2019.00064>
- 1185 Creed, I., Noordwijk, M. van, Archer, E., Claassen, M., Ellison, D., Jones, J. A., McNulty, S. G., Vira, B., & Wei, X. (Adam).
1186 (2018). Forest, trees and water on a changing planet: How contemporary science can inform policy and
1187 practice. *In: Forest and Water on a Changing Planet: Vulnerability, Adaptation and Governance Opportunities:*
1188 *A Global Assessment Report* (I.F. Creed and M. van Noordwijk, Eds.). IUFRO World Series, 38, 171–175.
- 1189 Crist, E., Mora, C., & Engelman, R. (2017). The interaction of human population, food production, and biodiversity
1190 protection. *Science*, 356(6335), 260–264. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aal2011>
- 1191 Deininger, A., & Frigstad, H. (2019). Reevaluating the Role of Organic Matter Sources for Coastal Eutrophication,
1192 Oligotrophication, and Ecosystem Health. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 6, 210.
1193 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2019.00210>

- 1194 Dempsey, J., Martin, T. G., & Sumaila, U. R. (2020). Subsidizing extinction? *Conservation Letters*.
1195 <https://doi.org/10.1111/conl.12705>
- 1196 Deng, Y., Wang, S., Bai, X., Luo, G., Wu, L., Chen, F., Wang, J., Li, C., Yang, Y., Hu, Z., Tian, S., & Lu, Q. (2020). Vegetation
1197 greening intensified soil drying in some semi-arid and arid areas of the world. *Agricultural and Forest*
1198 *Meteorology*, 292–293, 108103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agrformet.2020.108103>
- 1199 Diaz, Sandra, Settele, J., Brondízio, E., Ngo, H. T., Agard, J., Arneth, A., Balvanera, P., Brauman, K., Butchart, S., Chan,
1200 K., Garibaldi, L., Ichii, K., Liu, J., Subramanian, S., Midgley, G., Miloslavich, P., Molnár, Z., Obura, D., Pfaff, A.,
1201 & Zayas, C. (2019). Pervasive human-driven decline of life on Earth points to the need for transformative
1202 change. *Science (New York, N.Y.)*, 366. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aax3100>
- 1203 Dinerstein, E., Joshi, A. R., Vynne, C., Lee, A. T. L., Pharand-Deschênes, F., França, M., Fernando, S., Birch, T., Burkart,
1204 K., Asner, G. P., & Olson, D. (2020). A “Global Safety Net” to reverse biodiversity loss and stabilize Earth’s
1205 climate. *Science Advances*, 6(36), eabb2824. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.abb2824>
- 1206 Dinerstein, E., Olson, D., Joshi, A., Vynne, C., Burgess, N. D., Wikramanayake, E., Hahn, N., Palminteri, S., Hedao, P.,
1207 Noss, R., Hansen, M., Locke, H., Ellis, E. C., Jones, B., Barber, C. V., Hayes, R., Kormos, C., Martin, V., Crist, E.,
1208 ... Saleem, M. (2017). An Ecoregion-Based Approach to Protecting Half the Terrestrial Realm. *Bioscience*,
1209 67(6), 534–545. <https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/bix014>
- 1210 Ditchburn, J.-L., & Carballeira, C. B. (2019). Versatility of the Humble Seaweed in Biomanufacturing. 12th
1211 International Conference Interdisciplinarity in Engineering, INTER-ENG 2018, 4–5 October 2018, Tirgu Mures,
1212 Romania, 32, 87–94. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.promfg.2019.02.187>
- 1213 Donato, D. C., Kauffman, J. B., Murdiyarsa, D., Kurnianto, S., Stidham, M., & Kanninen, M. (2011). Mangroves among
1214 the most carbon-rich forests in the tropics. *Nature Geoscience*, 4(5), 293–297.
1215 <https://doi.org/10.1038/ngeo1123>
- 1216 Donohue, R. J., Roderick, M. L., McVicar, T. R., & Farquhar, G. D. (2013). Impact of CO2 fertilization on maximum
1217 foliage cover across the globe’s warm, arid environments. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 40(12), 3031–3035.
1218 <https://doi.org/10.1002/grl.50563>
- 1219 Doré, T., Makowski, D., Malézieux, E., Munier-Jolain, N., Tchamitchian, M., & Tittone, P. (2011). Facing up to the
1220 paradigm of ecological intensification in agronomy: Revisiting methods, concepts and knowledge. *European*
1221 *Journal of Agronomy*, 34(4), 197–210. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eja.2011.02.006>
- 1222 Duarte, Wu, J., Xiao, X., Bruhn, A., & Krause-Jensen, D. (2017). Can Seaweed Farming Play a Role in Climate Change
1223 Mitigation and Adaptation? In *Frontiers in Marine Science*. *Frontiers Media SA*.
1224 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2017.00100>
- 1225 Duveiller, G., Caporaso, L., Abad-Vinas, R., Perugini, L., Grassi, G., Arneth, A., & Cescatti, A. (2020). Local biophysical
1226 effects of land use and land cover change: Towards an assessment tool for policy makers. *Land Use Policy*,
1227 91. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2019.104382>
- 1228 L. Egli, C. Meyer, C. Scherber, H. Kreft, T. Tschardt. Winners and losers of national and global efforts to reconcile
1229 agricultural intensification and biodiversity conservation. *Glob Change Biol*, 24 (2018), pp. 2212-2228.
1230 <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.14076>
- 1231 Ekawati, S., Subarudi, Budiningsih, K., Sari, G. K., & Muttaqin, M. Z. (2019). Policies affecting the implementation of
1232 REDD+ in Indonesia (cases in Papua, Riau and Central Kalimantan). *Assessing Policies to Reduce Emissions*
1233 *from Land Use Change in Indonesia*, 108, 101939. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forpol.2019.05.025>
- 1234 Engle, V. (2011). Estimating the Provision of Ecosystem Services by Gulf of Mexico Coastal Wetlands. *Wetlands*, 31,
1235 179–193. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13157-010-0132-9>
- 1236 Enquist, B. J., Feng, X., Boyle, B., Maitner, B., Newman, E. A., Jørgensen, P. M., Roehrdanz, P. R., Thiers, B. M., Burger,
1237 J. R., Corlett, R. T., Couvreur, T. L. P., Dauby, G., Donoghue, J. C., Foden, W., Lovett, J. C., Marquet, P. A.,
1238 Merow, C., Midgley, G., Morueta-Holme, N., ... McGill, B. J. (2019). The commonness of rarity: Global and

1239 future distribution of rarity across land plants. *Science Advances*, 5(11), eaaz0414.
1240 <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.aaz0414>

1241 Enzi, V., Cameron, B., Dezsényi, P., Gedge, D., Mann, G., & Pitha, U. (2017). Nature-Based Solutions and Buildings –
1242 The Power of Surfaces to Help Cities Adapt to Climate Change and to Deliver Biodiversity (pp. 159–183).
1243 https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-56091-5_10

1244 Epple, C., Rangel, G., Jenkins, M., & Guth, M. (2016). Managing ecosystems in the context of climate change
1245 mitigation: A review of current knowledge and recommendations to support ecosystem-based mitigation
1246 actions that look beyond terrestrial forests. Secretariat of the Convention on Biological Diversity.

1247 Ermgassen, Sophus O. S. E. zu, Baker, J., Griffiths, R. A., Strange, N., Struebig, M. J., & Bull, J. W. (2019). The ecological
1248 outcomes of biodiversity offsets under “no net loss” policies: A global review. *Conservation Letters*, 12(6),
1249 e12664. <https://doi.org/10.1111/conl.12664>

1250 Estes, L. D., Searchinger, T., Spiegel, M., Tian, D., Sichinga, S., Mwale, M., Kehoe, L., Kuemmerle, T., Berven, A.,
1251 Chaney, N., Sheffield, J., Wood, E. F., & Caylor, K. K. (2016). Reconciling agriculture, carbon and biodiversity
1252 in a savannah transformation frontier. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*.
1253 <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2015.0316>

1254 Falk, J. M., Schmidt, N. M., Christensen, T. R., & Ström, L. (2015). Large herbivore grazing affects the vegetation
1255 structure and greenhouse gas balance in a high arctic mire. *Environmental Research Letters*, 10(4), 045001.
1256 <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/10/4/045001>

1257 FAO. 2019a. Climate-smart agriculture and the Sustainable Development Goals: Mapping interlinkages, synergies
1258 and trade-offs and guidelines for integrated implementation. Rome.

1259 FAO. (2019b). The State of the World’s Biodiversity for Food and Agriculture. FAO Commission on Genetic Resources
1260 for Food and Agriculture Assessments. <http://www.fao.org/3/CA3129EN/CA3129EN.pdf>

1261 Fearnside, P. M. (2016). Greenhouse gas emissions from Brazil’s Amazonian hydroelectric dams. *Environmental
1262 Research Letters*, 11(1), 011002. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/11/1/011002>

1263 Fensholt, R., Langanke, T., Rasmussen, K., Reenberg, A., Prince, S. D., Tucker, C., Scholes, R. J., Le, Q. B., Bondeau, A.,
1264 Eastman, R., Epstein, H., Gaughan, A. E., Hellden, U., Mbow, C., Olsson, L., Paruelo, J., Schweitzer, C., Seaquist,
1265 J., & Wessels, K. (2012). Greenness in semi-arid areas across the globe 1981–2007—An Earth Observing
1266 Satellite based analysis of trends and drivers. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 121, 144–158.
1267 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2012.01.017>

1268 Fisher, B., Turner, R. K., & Morling, P. (2009). Defining and classifying ecosystem services for decision making.
1269 *Ecological Economics*, 68(3), 643–653. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2008.09.014>

1270 Franks, M., Lessmann, K., Jakob, M., Steckel, J. C., & Edenhofer, O. (2018). Mobilizing domestic resources for the
1271 Agenda 2030 via carbon pricing. *Nature Sustainability*, 1(7), 350–357. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-018-0083-3>
1272

1273 Friedlingstein, P., O’Sullivan, M., Jones, M. W., Andrew, R. M., Hauck, J., Olsen, A., Peters, G. P., Peters, W., Pongratz,
1274 J., Sitch, S., Le Quéré, C., Canadell, J. G., Ciais, P., Jackson, R. B., Alin, S., Aragão, L. E. O. C., Arneeth, A., Arora,
1275 V., Bates, N. R., Becker, M., Benoit-Cattin, A., Bittig, H. C., Bopp, L., Bultan, S., Chandra, N., Chevallier, F., Chini,
1276 L. P., Evans, W., Florentie, L., Forster, P. M., Gasser, T., Gehlen, M., Gilfillan, D., Gkritzalis, T., Gregor, L.,
1277 Gruber, N., Harris, I., Hartung, K., Haverd, V., Houghton, R. A., Ilyina, T., Jain, A. K., Joetzjer, E., Kadono, K.,
1278 Kato, E., Kitidis, V., Korsbakken, J. I., Landschützer, P., Lefèvre, N., Lenton, A., Lienert, S., Liu, Z., Lombardozzi,
1279 D., Marland, G., Metzl, N., Munro, D. R., Nabel, J. E. M. S., Nakaoka, S.-I., Niwa, Y., O’Brien, K., Ono, T., Palmer,
1280 P. I., Pierrot, D., Poulter, B., Resplandy, L., Robertson, E., Rödenbeck, C., Schwinger, J., Séférian, R., Skjelvan,
1281 I., Smith, A. J. P., Sutton, A. J., Tanhua, T., Tans, P. P., Tian, H., Tilbrook, B., van der Werf, G., Vuichard, N.,
1282 Walker, A. P., Wanninkhof, R., Watson, A. J., Willis, D., Wiltshire, A. J., Yuan, W., Yue, X., and Zaehle, S.: Global
1283 Carbon Budget 2020, *Earth Syst. Sci. Data*, 12, 3269–3340, <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-12-3269-2020>, 2020.
1284 Friess, D. A., Richards, D. R., & Phang, V. X. H. (2015). Mangrove forests store high densities of carbon across
1285 the tropical urban landscape of Singapore. *Urban Ecosystem*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11252-015-0511-3>

- 1286 Froehlich, H. E., Afflerbach, J. C., Frazier, M., & Halpern, B. S. (2019). Blue Growth Potential to Mitigate Climate
1287 Change through Seaweed Offsetting. *Current Biology*, 29(18), 3087-3093.e3.
1288 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2019.07.041>
- 1289 Gallego-Sala, A. V., Charman, D. J., Brewer, S., Page, S. E., Prentice, I. C., Friedlingstein, P., Moreton, S., Amesbury,
1290 M. J., Beilman, D. W., Björck, S., Blyakharchuk, T., Bochicchio, C., Booth, R. K., Bunbury, J., Camill, P., Carless,
1291 D., Chimner, R. A., Clifford, M., Cressey, E., ... Zhao, Y. (2018). Latitudinal limits to the predicted increase of
1292 the peatland carbon sink with warming. *Nature Climate Change*, 8(10), 907–913.
1293 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-018-0271-1>
- 1294 James N. Galloway, John D. Aber, Jan Willem Erisman, Sybil P. Seitzinger, Robert W. Howarth, Ellis B. Cowling, B. Jack
1295 Cosby, The Nitrogen Cascade, *BioScience*, Volume 53, Issue 4, April 2003, Pages 341–356,
1296 [https://doi.org/10.1641/0006-3568\(2003\)053\[0341:TNC\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1641/0006-3568(2003)053[0341:TNC]2.0.CO;2)
- 1297 Gerber, J.S., Carlson, K.M., Garcia de Cortazar-Atauri, I., Herrero, M., Launay, M., Makowski, D., Mueller, N.D.,
1298 O'Connell, C.S., Smith, P. & West, P.C. 2016. Spatially explicit N₂O emissions estimates suggest climate
1299 mitigation opportunities from improved nitrogen management. *Global Change Biology* 22, 3383–3394. doi:
1300 10.1111/gcb.13341.
- 1301 Gil, J.D.B., Cohn, A.S., Duncan, J., Newton, P., Vermeulen, S. (2017). The resilience of integrated agricultural systems
1302 to climate change. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change* 8.
- 1303 Giller, K. E., Hijbeek, R., Andersson, J. A. & Sumberg, J. (2021). Regenerative agriculture: An agronomic perspective.
1304 *Outlook on Agriculture* (in press), <https://doi.org/10.1177/0030727021998063>
- 1305 Girardin CAJ, Jenkins S, Seddon N, Allen M, Lewis SL, Wheeler CE, Griscom BW, Malhi Y, et al. 2021. Nature-based
1306 solutions can help cool the planet — if we act now. *Nature* 593:191-194
- 1307 Gizachew, B., Astrup, R., Vedeld, P., Zahabu, E. M., & Duguma, L. A. (2017). REDD+ in Africa: Contexts and challenges.
1308 *Natural Resources Forum*, 41(2), 92–104. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1477-8947.12119>
- 1309 Godfray, H.C.J., 2015: The debate over sustainable intensification. *Food Secur.*, 7, 199–208, doi:10.1007/s12571-
1310 015-0424-2.
- 1311 Gosnell, H., Grimm, K., & Goldstein, B. E. (2020). A half century of Holistic Management: What does the evidence
1312 reveal? *Agriculture and Human Values*, 37(3), 849–867. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10460-020-10016-w>
- 1313 Green, R. E., Cornell, S. J., Scharlemann, J. P. W., & Balmford, A. (2005). Farming and the Fate of Wild Nature. *Science*,
1314 307(5709), 550–555. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1106049>
- 1315 Griffith, A., & Gobler, C. (2019). Harmful algal blooms: A climate change co-stressor in marine and freshwater
1316 ecosystems. *Harmful Algae*, 91. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2019.03.008>
- 1317 Griscom, B. W., Adams, J., Ellis, P. W., Houghton, R. A., Lomax, G., Miteva, D. A., Schlesinger, W. H., Shoch, D.,
1318 Siikamäki, J. V., Smith, P., Woodbury, P., Zganjar, C., Blackman, A., Campari, J., Conant, R. T., Delgado, C., Elias,
1319 P., Gopalakrishna, T., Hamsik, M. R., ... Fargione, J. (2017). Natural climate solutions. In *Proceedings of the*
1320 *National Academy of Sciences* (Vol. 114, Issue 44, pp. 11645–11650).
1321 <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1710465114>
- 1322 Guannel, G., Arkema, K., Ruggiero, P., & Verutes, G. (2016). The power of three: Coral reefs, seagrasses and
1323 mangroves protect coastal regions and increase their resilience. *PloS One*, 11(7), e0158094.
1324 <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0158094>
- 1325 Gullison, R. E., Frumhoff, P. C., Canadell, J. G., Field, C. B., Nepstad, D. C., Hayhoe, K., Avissar, R., Curran, L. M.,
1326 Friedlingstein, P., Jones, C. D., & Nobre, C. (2007). ENVIRONMENT: Tropical Forests and Climate Policy.
1327 *Science*, 316(5827), 985–986. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1136163>
- 1328 Gustavsson, J., Cederberg, C., & Sonesson, U. (2011). Global food losses and food waste: Extent, causes and
1329 prevention ; study conducted for the International Congress Save Food! at Interpack 2011, [16 - 17 May],
1330 Düsseldorf, Germany. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.

- 1331 Hannah, L., Roehrdanz, P. R., Marquet, P. A., Enquist, B. J., Midgley, G., Foden, W., Lovett, J. C., Corlett, R. T.,
 1332 Corcoran, D., Butchart, S. H. M., Boyle, B., Feng, X., Maitner, B., Fajardo, J., McGill, B. J., Merow, C., Morueta-
 1333 Holme, N., Newman, E. A., Park, D. S., ... Svenning, J.-C. (2020). 30% land conservation and climate action
 1334 reduces tropical extinction risk by more than 50%. *Ecography*, 43(943–953).
 1335 <https://doi.org/10.1111/ecog.05166>
- 1336 Harlio, A., Kuussaari, M., Heikkinen, R. K., & Arponen, A. (2019). Incorporating landscape heterogeneity into multi-
 1337 objective spatial planning improves biodiversity conservation of semi-natural grasslands. *Journal for Nature*
 1338 *Conservation*, 49, 37–44. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnc.2019.01.003>
- 1339 Hayek, M. N., Harwatt, H., Ripple, W. J., & Mueller, N. D. (2021). The carbon opportunity cost of animal-sourced food
 1340 production on land. *Nature Sustainability*, 4(1), 21–24. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-020-00603-4>
- 1341 Heilmayr, R., Echeverría, C., & Lambin, E. F. (2020). Impacts of Chilean forest subsidies on forest cover, carbon and
 1342 biodiversity. *Nature Sustainability*, 3(9), 701–709. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-020-0547-0>
- 1343 Heithaus, M. R., Alcoverro, T., Arthur, R., Burkholder, D. A., Coates, K. A., Christianen, M. J. A., Kelkar, N., Manuel, S.
 1344 A., Wirsing, A. J., Kenworthy, W. J., & Fourqurean, J. W. (2014). Seagrasses in the age of sea turtle conservation
 1345 and shark overfishing. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 1. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2014.00028>
- 1346 Hoegh-Guldberg, O., D. Jacob, M. Taylor, M. Bindi, S. Brown, I. Camilloni, A. Diedhiou, R. Djalante, K.L. Ebi, F.
 1347 Engelbrecht, J. Guiot, Y. Hijjoka, S. Mehrotra, A. Payne, S.I. Seneviratne, A. Thomas, R. Warren, and G. Zhou,
 1348 2018: Impacts of 1.5°C Global Warming on Natural and Human Systems. In: *Global Warming of 1.5°C. An IPCC*
 1349 *Special Report on the impacts of global warming of 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels and related global*
 1350 *greenhouse gas emission pathways, in the context of strengthening the global response to the threat of*
 1351 *climate change, sustainable development, and efforts to eradicate poverty* [Masson-Delmotte, V., P. Zhai, H.-
 1352 O. Pörtner, D. Roberts, J. Skea, P.R. Shukla, A. Pirani, W. Moufouma-Okia, C. Péan, R. Pidcock, S. Connors,
 1353 J.B.R. Matthews, Y. Chen, X. Zhou, M.I. Gomis, E. Lonnoy, T. Maycock, M. Tignor, and T. Waterfield (eds.)].
- 1354 Huntley, B. J., & Redford, K. H. (2014). *Mainstreaming Biodiversity in Practice: A STAP Advisory Document*. Global
 1355 Environment Facility.
- 1356 IPBES. (2018). The IPBES assessment report on land degradation and restoration (p. 744). Secretariat of the
 1357 Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services,.
- 1358 IPBES. (2019a). *Global assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services of the Intergovernmental Science-*
 1359 *Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services*. IPBES secretariat.
- 1360 IPBES, 2019b: *Glossary*. Secretariat of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem
 1361 services, Bonn, Germany. Retrieved from: <https://www.ipbes.net/glossary>.
- 1362 IPCC (2013). *Climate Change 2013: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Fifth*
 1363 *Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change* [Stocker, T.F., D. Qin, G.-K. Plattner,
 1364 M. Tignor, S.K. Allen, J. Boschung, A. Nauels, Y. Xia, V. Bex and P.M. Midgley (eds.)]. Cambridge University
 1365 Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA, 1535 pp.
- 1366 IPCC (2014). *Climate Change 2014: Impacts, Adaptation, and Vulnerability. Part A: Global and Sectoral Aspects.*
 1367 *Contribution of Working Group II to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate*
 1368 *Change* [Field, C.B., V.R. Barros, D.J. Dokken, K.J. Mach, M.D. Mastrandrea, T.E. Bilir, M. Chatterjee, K.L. Ebi,
 1369 Y.O. Estrada, R.C. Genova, B. Girma, E.S. Kissel, A.N. Levy, S. MacCracken, P.R. Mastrandrea, and L.L. White
 1370 (eds.)]. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA, 1132 pp
- 1371 IPCC (2019). *Climate Change and Land: an IPCC special report on climate change, desertification, land degradation,*
 1372 *sustainable land management, food security, and greenhouse gas fluxes in terrestrial ecosystems* [P.R. Shukla,
 1373 J. Skea, E. Calvo Buendía, V. Masson-Delmotte, H.-O. Pörtner, D. C. Roberts, P. Zhai, R. Slade, S. Connors, R.
 1374 van Diemen, M. Ferrat, E. Haughey, S. Luz, S. Neogi, M. Pathak, J. Petzold, J. Portugal Pereira, P. Vyas, E.
 1375 Huntley, K. Kissick, M. Belkacemi, J. Malley, (eds.)]. In press.

- 1376 Ise, T., Dunn, A. L., Wofsy, S. C., & Moorcroft, P. R. (2008). High sensitivity of peat decomposition to climate change
1377 through water-table feedback. *Nature Geoscience*, 1(11), 763–766. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ngeo331>
- 1378 IUCN. (2017). *The Sundarbans 2017 Conservation Outlook Assessment*. IUCN.
- 1379 IUCN. (2020). *Sundarbans National Park 2020 Conservation Outlook Assessment* (p. 24 [2020 Conservation Outlook
1380 Assessment]). IUCN.
- 1381 Jahangir, M. M. R., Richards, K., Healy, M., Gill, L., Müller, C., Johnston, P., & Fenton, O. (2016). Carbon and nitrogen
1382 dynamics and greenhouse gas emissions in constructed wetlands treating wastewater: A review. *Hydrology
1383 and Earth System Sciences*, 20, 109–123. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-20-109-2016>
- 1384 Jantz, P., Goetz, S., & Laporte, N. (2014). Carbon stock corridors to mitigate climate change and promote biodiversity
1385 in the tropics. *Nature Climate Change*, 4(2), 138–142. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate2105>
- 1386 Jia, G., Shevliakova, E., Artaxo, P., De Noblet-Ducoudre, N., Houghton, R., House, J., Kitajima, K., Lennard, C., Popp,
1387 A., Sirin, A., Sukumar, R., & Verchot, L. (2019b). Land–climate interactions. In *Climate Change and Land: An
1388 IPCC special report on climate change, desertification, land degradation, sustainable land management, food
1389 security, and greenhouse gas fluxes in terrestrial ecosystems* [P.R. Shukla, J. Skea, E. Calvo Buendia, V.
1390 Masson-Delmotte, H.-O. Pörtner, D.C. Roberts, P. Zhai, R. Slade, S. Connors, R. van Diemen, M. Ferrat, E.
1391 Haughey, S. Luz, S. Neogi, M. Pathak, J. Petzold, J. Portugal Pereira, P. Vyas, E. Huntley, K. Kissick, M,
1392 Belkacemi, J. Malley, (eds.)] (pp. 131–247).
- 1393 Johnson, B. A., Dasgupta, R., Mader, A. D., & Scheyvens, H. (2019). Understanding national biodiversity targets in a
1394 REDD+ context. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 92, 27–33. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2018.11.007>
- 1395 Joly, C. A., Scarano, F. R., Bustamante, M., Gadda, T., Metzger, J. P., Seixas, C. S., Ometto, J.-P., Pires, A. P. F., Boesing,
1396 A. L., Sousa, F. D. R., Quintão, J. M., Gonçalves, L., Padgurschi, M. C. G., Aquino, M. F. S. de, Castro, P. D. de,
1397 & Santos, I. de L. (2018). Sumário para tomadores de decisão: 1o diagnóstico brasileiro de biodiversidade e
1398 serviços ecossistêmicos. 10.5935. <https://doi.org/10.5935/978-85-5697-707-6>
- 1399 Jones, J. P. G., Bull, J. W., Roe, D., Baker, J., Griffiths, V. F., Starkey, M., Sonter, L. J., & Milner-Gulland, E. J. (2019).
1400 Net Gain: Seeking Better Outcomes for Local People when Mitigating Biodiversity Loss from Development.
1401 *One Earth*, 1(2), 195–201. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2019.09.007>
- 1402 Joshi, S., Liang, Y., Wang, J., Pasakhala, B., Ismail, M., Bisht, N., Qamer, F. M., Long, R., Ning, W., Foggin, M., Weikang,
1403 Y., Bari, F., Shokirov, Q., Ahmed, A., Essa, M., & Wenxuan, X. (2019). Rangeland resource and use assessment
1404 protocol. International Centre for Integrated Mountain Development GPO Box 3226, Kathmandu, Nepal ISBN:
1405 ISBN 978 92 9115 687 0 (electronic)
- 1406 Keeley, A. T. H., Basson, G., Cameron, D. R., Heller, N. E., Huber, P. R., Schloss, C. A., Thorne, J. H., & Merenlender, A.
1407 M. (2018b). Making habitat connectivity a reality. *Conservation Biology*, 32(6), 1221–1232.
1408 <https://doi.org/10.1111/cobi.13158>
- 1409 Kemppinen, K. M. S., Collins, P. M., Hole, D. G., Wolf, C., Ripple, W. J., & Gerber, L. R. (2020). Global reforestation
1410 and biodiversity conservation. *Conservation Biology*, 34(5), 1221–1228. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cobi.13478>
- 1411 Kier, G., Mutke, J., Dinerstein, E., Ricketts, T. H., Küper, W., Kreft, H., & Barthlott, W. (2005). Global patterns of plant
1412 diversity and floristic knowledge: Global plant diversity. *Journal of Biogeography*, 32(7), 1107–1116.
1413 <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2699.2005.01272.x>
- 1414 Kremen, C. (2015) Reframing the land-sparing/land-sharing debate for biodiversity conservation. *Annals of the New
1415 York Academy of Sciences*, 1355, 52– 76. DOI: 10.1111/nyas.12845
- 1416 Laurance, W. F., Sayer, J., & Cassman, K. G. (2014). Agricultural expansion and its impacts on tropical nature. *Trends
1417 in Ecology & Evolution*, 29(2), 107–116. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2013.12.001>
- 1418 Lavery, T. J., Roudnew, B., Gill, P., Seymour, J., Seuront, L., Johnson, G., Mitchell, J. G., & Smetacek, V. (2010). Iron
1419 defecation by sperm whales stimulates carbon export in the Southern Ocean. *Proceedings of the Royal
1420 Society B: Biological Sciences*, 277(1699), 3527–3531. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2010.0863>

- 1421 Leippert, F., Darmaun, M., Bernoux, M. and Mpheshea, M. 2020. The potential of agroecology to build climate-
1422 resilient livelihoods and food systems. Rome. FAO and Biovision. <https://doi.org/10.4060/cb0438en>
- 1423 Lewis, Simon L., Wheeler, C. E., Mitchard, E. T. A., & Koch, A. (2019). Restoring natural forests is the best way to
1424 remove atmospheric carbon. *Nature*, 568(7750), 25–28. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-019-01026-8>
- 1425 Liniger, H. P., Bandy, J., Bhuchar, S., & Joshi, R. (2020). Spring Revival through Sustainable Land Management (SLM)
1426 in the Himalayan foothills: Uttarakhand, North India. WOCAT SLM Policy Brief, No. 1. WOCAT.
- 1427 Linsy, P., Nagender Nath, B., Mascarenhas-Pereira, M. B. L., Vinitha, P. V., Ray, D., Prakash Babu, C., Ramalingeswara
1428 Rao, B., Kazip, A., Sebastian, T., Kocherla, M., & Miriyala, P. (2018). Benthic cycling of phosphorus in the
1429 Eastern Arabian Sea: Evidence of present day phosphogenesis. *Marine Chemistry*, 199, 53–66.
1430 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marchem.2018.01.007>
- 1431 Lipper, L., Thornton, P., Campbell, B. M., Baedeker, T., Braimoh, A., Bwalya, M., Caron, P., Cattaneo, A., Garrity, D.,
1432 Henry, K., Hottle, R., Jackson, L., Jarvis, A., Kossam, F., Mann, W., McCarthy, N., Meybeck, A., Neufeldt, H.,
1433 Remington, T., ... Torquebiau, E. F. (2014). Climate-smart agriculture for food security. *Nature Climate Change*,
1434 4(12), 1068–1072. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate2437>
- 1435 Littlefield, C. E., Krosby, M., Michalak, J. L., & Lawler, J. J. (2019). Connectivity for species on the move: Supporting
1436 climate-driven range shifts. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment*, 17(5), 270–278.
1437 <https://doi.org/10.1002/fee.2043>
- 1438 Linsy, P., Nagender Nath, B., Mascarenhas-Pereira, M. B. L., Vinitha, P. V., Ray, D., Babu, C. P., et al. (2018). Benthic
1439 cycling of phosphorus in the Eastern Arabian Sea: Evidence of present day phosphogenesis. *Marine*
1440 *Chemistry*, 199, 53–66. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marchem.2018.01.007>
- 1441 Liu, L., W. Xu, Q. Yue, X. Teng, and H. Hu. (2018). Problems and Countermeasures of Coastline Protection and
1442 Utilization in China. *Ocean & Coastal Management* 153 (March): 124–30.
1443 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2017.12.016>.
- 1444 Locke, H., Ellis, E. C., Venter, O., Schuster, R., Ma, K., Shen, X., Woodley, S., Kingston, N., Bhola, N., Strassburg, B. B.
1445 N., Paulsch, A., Williams, B., & Watson, J. E. M. (2019). Three Global Conditions for Biodiversity Conservation
1446 and Sustainable Use: An implementation framework. *National Science Review*, nzw136.
1447 <https://doi.org/10.1093/nsr/nwz136>
- 1448 Loke, L.H.L., E.C. Heery, and P.A. Todd. 2019. Shoreline Defences. In *World Seas: An Environmental Evaluation*, vol.
1449 3, *Ecological Issues and Environmental Impacts*, edited by C. Sheppard, 491–504. 2nd ed. London: Academic
1450 Press.
- 1451 Lomnitz, U., Sommer, S., Dale, A. W., Löscher, C. R., Noffke, A., Wallmann, K., & Hensen, C. (2016). Benthic
1452 phosphorus cycling in the Peruvian oxygen minimum zone. *Biogeosciences*, 13(5), 1367–1386.
1453 <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-13-1367-2016>
- 1454 Lundberg, S., & Marklund, P.-O. (2018). Green public procurement and multiple environmental objectives. *Economia*
1455 *e Politica Industriale*, 45(1), 37–53. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40812-017-0085-6>
- 1456 Mackey, B., Kormos, C. F., Keith, H., Moomaw, W. R., Houghton, R. A., Mittermeier, R. A., Hole, D., & Hugh, S. (2020).
1457 Understanding the importance of primary tropical forest protection as a mitigation strategy. *Mitigation and*
1458 *Adaptation Strategies for Global Change*, 25(5), 763–787. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11027-019-09891-4>
- 1459 Malhi, Y., Doughty, C. E., Galetti, M., Smith, F. A., Svenning, J. C., & Terborgh, J. W. (2016). Megafauna and ecosystem
1460 function from the Pleistocene to the Anthropocene. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the*
1461 *United States of America*, 113(4), 838–846. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1502540113>
- 1462 Malhi, Y., Roberts, J. T., Betts, R. A., Killeen, T. J., Li, W., & Nobre, C. A. (2008). Climate Change, Deforestation, and
1463 the Fate of the Amazon. *Science*, 319(5860), 169–172. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1146961>

- 1464 Mariani, G., Cheung, W. W. L., Lyet, A., Sala, E., Mayorga, J., Velez, L., Gaines, S. D., Dejean, T., Troussellier, M., &
 1465 Mouillot, D. (2020). Let more big fish sink: Fisheries prevent blue carbon sequestration—half in unprofitable
 1466 areas. *Science Advances*, 6(44), eabb4848. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.abb4848>
- 1467 Matricardi, E. A. T., Skole, D. L., Costa, O. B., Pedlowski, M. A., Samek, J. H., & Miguel, E. P. (2020). Long-term forest
 1468 degradation surpasses deforestation in the Brazilian Amazon. *Science*, 369(6509), 1378–1382.
 1469 <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abb3021>
- 1470 Maxton-Lee, B. (2018). Material Realities: Why Indonesian Deforestation Persists and Conservation Fails. *Journal of*
 1471 *Contemporary Asia*, 48(3), 419–444. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00472336.2017.1402204>
- 1472 Maxwell, S. L., Evans, T., Watson, J. E. M., Morel, A., Grantham, H., Duncan, A., Harris, N., Potapov, P., Runting, R. K.,
 1473 Venter, O., Wang, S., & Malhi, Y. (2019). Degradation and forgone removals increase the carbon impact of
 1474 intact forest loss by 626%. *Science Advances*, 5(10). <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.aax2546>
- 1475 Mbow, C., M. Van Noordwijk, E. Luedeling, H. Neufeldt, P.A. Minang, and G. Kowero, 2014: Agroforestry solutions
 1476 to address food security and climate change challenges in Africa. *Curr. Opin. Environ. Sustain.*, 6, 61–67,
 1477 doi:10.1016/j.cosust.2013.10.014.
- 1478 McFarland, W., Whitley, S., & Kissinger, G. (2015). Subsidies to key commodities driving forest loss.
 1479 [https://static1.squarespace.com/static/58d6cc1e17bffcffb801edde/t/5970e3c6e3df28c64461c095/150057](https://static1.squarespace.com/static/58d6cc1e17bffcffb801edde/t/5970e3c6e3df28c64461c095/1500570579966/Subsidies+driving+forest+loss.pdf)
 1480 [0579966/Subsidies+driving+forest+loss.pdf](https://static1.squarespace.com/static/58d6cc1e17bffcffb801edde/t/5970e3c6e3df28c64461c095/1500570579966/Subsidies+driving+forest+loss.pdf)
- 1481 Mcleod, E., Chmura, G. L., Bouillon, S., Salm, R., Björk, M., Duarte, C. M., Lovelock, C. E., Schlesinger, W. H., & Silliman,
 1482 B. R. (2011). A blueprint for blue carbon: Toward an improved understanding of the role of vegetated coastal
 1483 habitats in sequestering CO₂. 9(10), 552–560. <https://doi.org/10.1890/110004>
- 1484 Melillo, J. M., Lu, X., Kicklighter, D. W., Reilly, J. M., Cai, Y., & Sokolov, A. P. (2016). Protected areas' role in climate-
 1485 change mitigation. *Ambio*, 45(2), 133–145. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-015-0693-1>
- 1486 Ministry of Environment and Tourism. (2011). Namibia Second National Communication to the United Nations
 1487 Framework Convention on Climate Change.
- 1488 Moilanen, A., Franco, A. M. A., Early, R. I., Fox, R., Wintle, B., & Thomas, C. D. (2005). Prioritizing multiple-use
 1489 landscapes for conservation: Methods for large multi-species planning problems. *Proceedings of the Royal*
 1490 *Society B: Biological Sciences*, 272(1575), 1885–1891. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2005.3164>
- 1491 Muscatine, L., & D'Elia, C. F. (1978). The uptake, retention, and release of ammonium by reef corals 1. *Limnology*
 1492 *and Oceanography*, 23(4), 725–734. <https://doi.org/10.4319/lo.1978.23.4.0725>
- 1493 Mustin, K., Carvalho, W. D., Hilário, R. R., Costa-Neto, S. V., Silva, C., Vasconcelos, I. M., Castro, I. J., Eilers, V., Kauano,
 1494 É. E., Mendes-Junior, R. N. G., Funi, C., Fearnside, P. M., Silva, J. M. C., Euler, A. M. C., & Toledo, J. J. (2017).
 1495 Biodiversity, threats and conservation challenges in the Cerrado of Amapá, an Amazonian savanna. *Nature*
 1496 *Conservation*, 22, 107–127. <https://doi.org/10.3897/natureconservation.22.13823>
- 1497 Myers, R. A., & Worm, B. (2003). Rapid worldwide depletion of predatory fish communities. *Nature*, 423(6937), 280–
 1498 283. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature01610>
- 1499 Naqvi, S. W. A., Bange, H., Farias, L., Monteiro, P., Scranton, M., & J, Z. (2010). Marine Hypoxia/Anoxia as a Source
 1500 of CH₄ and N₂O. *Biogeosciences*, 7. <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-7-2159-2010>
- 1501 Nepal, M., Rai, R., Saudamini, D., Bhatta, L., Kotru, R., Khadayat, M., Rawal, R., & Gcs, N. (2018). Valuing Cultural
 1502 Services of the Kailash Sacred Landscape for Sustainable Management. *Sustainability*, 10.
 1503 <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10103638>
- 1504 Newbold, T., Hudson, L. N., Arnell, A. P., Contu, S., Palma, A. D., Ferrier, S., Hill, S. L. L., Hoskins, A. J., Lysenko, I.,
 1505 Phillips, H. R. P., Burton, V. J., Chng, C. W. T., Emerson, S., Gao, D., Pask-Hale, G., Hutton, J., Jung, M., Sanchez-
 1506 Ortiz, K., Simmons, B. I., ... Purvis, A. (2016). Has land use pushed terrestrial biodiversity beyond the planetary
 1507 boundary? A global assessment. *Science*, 353(6296), 288–291. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aaf2201>

- 1508 Newbold, T., Hudson, L. N., Hill, S. L. L., Contu, S., Lysenko, I., Senior, R. A., Börger, L., Bennett, D. J., Choimes, A.,
 1509 Collen, B., Day, J., Palma, A. D., Díaz, S., Echeverria-Londoño, S., Edgar, M. J., Feldman, A., Garon, M., Harrison,
 1510 M. L. K., Alhusseini, T., ... Purvis, A. (2015). Global effects of land use on local terrestrial biodiversity. *Nature*,
 1511 520(7545), 45–50. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature14324>
- 1512 Newmark, W. D., Jenkins, C. N., Pimm, S. L., McNeally, P. B., & Halley, J. M. (2017). Targeted habitat restoration can
 1513 reduce extinction rates in fragmented forests. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 114(36),
 1514 9635–9640. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1705834114>
- 1515 OECD. (2005). *Environmentally Harmful Subsidies*. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264012059-en>
- 1516 OECD. (2019). *Biodiversity: Finance and the Economic and Business Case for Action*, report prepared for the G7
 1517 Environment Ministers' Meeting, 5-6 May 2019. OECD.
- 1518 O'Leary, B. C., Winther-Janson, M., Bainbridge, J. M., Aitken, J., Hawkins, J. P., & Roberts, C. M. (2016). Effective
 1519 Coverage Targets for Ocean Protection. *Conservation Letters*, 9(6), 398–404.
 1520 <https://doi.org/10.1111/conl.12247>
- 1521 Opekunova, M. G., Opekunov, A. Yu., Kukushkin, S. Yu., & Arestova, I. Yu. (2018). Evaluation of Environmental
 1522 Transformation in Areas of Hydrocarbon Deposits in the North of Western Siberia. *Contemporary Problems*
 1523 *of Ecology*, 11(1), 99–110. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S1995425518010109>
- 1524 Oppenheimer, M., B.C. Glavovic, J. Hinkel, R. van de Wal, A.K. Magnan, A. Abd-Elgawad, R. Cai, M. Cifuentes-Jara,
 1525 R.M. DeConto, T. Ghosh, J. Hay, F. Isla, B. Marzeion, B. Meyssignac, and Z. Sebesvari, 2019: Sea Level Rise
 1526 and Implications for Low-Lying Islands, Coasts and Communities. In: *IPCC Special Report on the Ocean and*
 1527 *Cryosphere in a Changing Climate* [H.-O. Pörtner, D.C. Roberts, V. Masson-Delmotte, P. Zhai, M. Tignor, E.
 1528 Poloczanska, K. Mintenbeck, A. Alegría, M. Nicolai, A. Okem, J. Petzold, B. Rama, N.M. Weyer (eds.)].
- 1529 Pandey, A., Kotru, R., & Pradhan, N. (2016). Bridging cultural heritage, conservation and development through a
 1530 transboundary landscape approach. *Asian Sacred Natural Sites: Philosophy and Practice in Protected Areas*
 1531 *and Conservation*, 145–158. eBook ISBN 9781315676272
- 1532 Pangala, S. R., Enrich-Prast, A., Basso, L. S., Peixoto, R. B., Bastviken, D., Hornibrook, E. R. C., Gatti, L. V., Marotta, H.,
 1533 Calazans, L. S. B., Sakuragui, C. M., Bastos, W. R., Malm, O., Gloor, E., Miller, J. B., & Gauci, V. (2017). Large
 1534 emissions from floodplain trees close the Amazon methane budget. *Nature*, 552(7684), 230–234.
 1535 <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature24639>
- 1536 Passow, U., & Carlson, C. (2012). The biological pump in a high CO₂ world. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*,
 1537 470, 249–271. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps09985>
- 1538 Patra, P. K., Saeki, T., Dlugokencky, E. J., Ishijima, K., Umezawa, T., Ito, A., Aoki, S., Morimoto, S., Kort, E. A., Croswell,
 1539 A., Ravi Kumar, K., & Nakazawa, T. (2016). Regional Methane Emission Estimation Based on Observed
 1540 Atmospheric Concentrations (2002-2012). *Journal of the Meteorological Society of Japan. Ser. II*, 94(1), 91–
 1541 113. <https://doi.org/10.2151/jmsj.2016-006>
- 1542 Pearson, T.R.H., Brown, S., Murray, L. and Sidman, G. (2017) Greenhouse gas emissions from tropical forest
 1543 degradation: an underestimated source. *Carbon Balance and Management* 12.
 1544 <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13021-017-0072-2>
- 1545 Pershing, A. J., Christensen, L. B., Record, N. R., Sherwood, G. D., & Stetson, P. B. (2010). The Impact of Whaling on
 1546 the Ocean Carbon Cycle: Why Bigger Was Better. *PLoS ONE*, 5(8), e12444.
 1547 <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0012444>
- 1548 Perugini, L., Caporaso, L., Marconi, S., Cescatti, A., Quesada, B., de Noblet-Ducoudre, N., House, J., & Arneeth, A.
 1549 (2017). Biophysical effects on temperature and precipitation due to land cover change. *Environmental*
 1550 *Research Letters*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/aa6b3f>
- 1551 Peterson, D. A. (2001). Long Term Gravel Pad Reclamation on Alaska's North Slope. University of Minnesota,
 1552 Department of Horticultural Science. <http://hdl.handle.net/11299/60127>

- 1553 Phalan, B., Onial, M., Balmford, A., & Green, R. E. (2011). Reconciling Food Production and Biodiversity Conservation:
1554 Land Sharing and Land Sparing Compared. *Science*, 333(6047), 1289–1291.
1555 <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1208742>
- 1556 Piao, S., et al. (2006). Effect of climate and CO₂ changes on the greening of the Northern Hemisphere over the past
1557 two decades. *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 33(23): L23402. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2006GL028205>
- 1558 Pistorius, T., Carodenuto, S., & Wathum, G. (2017). Implementing Forest Landscape Restoration in Ethiopia. *Forests*,
1559 8(3), 61. <https://doi.org/10.3390/f8030061>
- 1560 Pitcher, G., & Jacinto, G. S. (2019). Ocean deoxygenation links to harmful algal blooms. In *Ocean deoxygenation:
1561 Everyone's problem* (pp. 153–170). IUCN International Union for Conservation of Nature.
- 1562 Plastrik, P., & Cleveland, J. (2018). *Life after carbon: The next Global Transformation of Cities*. Island Press.
- 1563 Poloczanska, E. S., Brown, C. J., Sydeman, W. J., Kiessling, W., Schoeman, D. S., Moore, P. J., Brander, K., Bruno, J. F.,
1564 Buckley, L. B., Burrows, M. T., Duarte, C. M., Halpern, B. S., Holding, J., Kappel, C. V., O'Connor, M. I., Pandolfi,
1565 J. M., Parmesan, C., Schwing, F., Thompson, S. A., & Richardson, A. J. (2013). Global imprint of climate change
1566 on marine life. *Nature Climate Change*, 3, 919–925. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate1958>
- 1567 Poloczanska, E. S., Burrows, M. T., Brown, C. J., García Molinos, J., Halpern, B. S., Hoegh-Guldberg, O., Kappel, C. V.,
1568 Moore, P. J., Richardson, A. J., & Schoeman, D. S. (2016). Responses of marine organisms to climate change
1569 across oceans. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 3, 62. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2016.00062>
- 1570 Pörtner, H.O., Scholes, R.J., Agard, J., Archer, E., Arneith, A., Bai, X., Barnes, D., Burrows, M., Chan, L., Cheung, W.L.,
1571 Diamond, S., Donatti, C., Duarte, C., Eisenhauer, N., Foden, W., Gasalla, M. A., Handa, C., Hickler, T., Hoegh-
1572 Guldberg, O., Ichii, K., Jacob, U., Insarov, G., Kiessling, W., Leadley, P., Leemans, R., Levin, L., Lim, M., Maharaj,
1573 S., Managi, S., Marquet, P. A., McElwee, P., Midgley, G., Oberdorff, T., Obura, D., Osman, E., Pandit, R.,
1574 Pascual, U., Pires, A. P. F., Popp, A., Reyes-García, V., Sankaran, M., Settele, J., Shin, Y. J., Sintayehu, D. W.,
1575 Smith, P., Steiner, N., Strassburg, B., Sukumar, R., Trisos, C., Val, A.L., Wu, J., Aldrian, E., Parmesan, C., Pichs-
1576 Madruga, R., Roberts, D.C., Rogers, A.D., Díaz, S., Fischer, M., Hashimoto, S., Lavorel, S., Wu, N., Ngo, H.T.
1577 2021. Scientific outcome of the IPBES-IPCC co-sponsored workshop on biodiversity and climate change; IPBES
1578 secretariat, Bonn, Germany, DOI:10.5281/zenodo.4659158.Pretty, J., Benton, T. G., Bharucha, Z. P., Dicks, L.
1579 V., Flora, C. B., Godfray, H. C. J., Goulson, D., Hartley, S., Lampkin, N., Morris, C., Pierzynski, G., Prasad, P. V.
1580 V., Reganold, J., Rockström, J., Smith, P., Thorne, P., & Wratten, S. (2018). Global assessment of agricultural
1581 system redesign for sustainable intensification. *Nature Sustainability*, 1(8), 441–446.
1582 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-018-0114-0>
- 1583 Pugh, T. A. M., Lindeskog, M., Smith, B., Poulter, B., Arneith, A., Haverd, V., & Calle, L. (2019). Role of forest regrowth
1584 in global carbon sink dynamics. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 201810512.
1585 <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1810512116>
- 1586 Queensland Department of Science, Information Technology and Innovation. (2017). *Land cover change in
1587 Queensland 2015–16: Statewide Landcover and Trees Study Report* (p. 57).
- 1588 Rabalais, N., Cai, W.-J., Carstensen, J., Conley, D., Fry, B., Hu, X., Quiñones-Rivera, Z., Rosenberg, R., Slomp, C. P.,
1589 Turner, R., Voss, M., Wissel, B., & Zhang, J. (2014). Eutrophication-Driven Deoxygenation in the Coastal Ocean.
1590 *Oceanography* (Washington D.C.), 27, 172–183. <https://doi.org/10.5670/oceanog.2014.21>
- 1591 Rao, Ch. S., Prasad, J. V. N. S., Choudhari, S. K. and A. K. Singh. 2020. Mainstreaming climate resilient villages in
1592 national programmes towards sustainability of agriculture and environment in India. *Climate Change and
1593 Environmental Sustainability* 2020, 8(2):116-133. DOI: 10.5958/2320-642X.2020.00013.7
- 1594 Reaka-Kudla ML (1997) The global biodiversity of coral reefs: a comparison with rain forests. Pp. 83-108 in Reaka-
1595 Kudla, M.L., D.E. Wilson, E.O. Wilson (eds.), *Biodiversity II: Understanding and Protecting our Biological
1596 Resources*. Washington, D.C., Joseph Henry Press, 551 pp

1597 Redford, K. H., Huntley, B. J., Roe, D., Hammond, T., Zimsky, M., Lovejoy, T. E., da Fonseca, G. A. B., Rodriguez, C. M.,
1598 & Cowling, R. M. (2015). Mainstreaming Biodiversity: Conservation for the Twenty-First Century. *Frontiers in*
1599 *Ecology and Evolution*, 3(Article 137), 1–7.

1600 Reisman-Berman, O., Keasar, T., & Tel-Zur, N. (2019). Native and non-native species for dryland afforestation:
1601 Bridging ecosystem integrity and livelihood support. *Annals of Forest Science*, 76(4), 114.
1602 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13595-019-0903-2>

1603 Roberts, C. M., O’Leary, B. C., & Hawkins, J. P. (2020). Climate change mitigation and nature conservation both
1604 require higher protected area targets. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*,
1605 375(1794). <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2019.0121>

1606 Roberts, C. M., O’Leary, B. C., McCauley, D. J., Cury, P. M., Duarte, C. M., Lubchenco, J., Pauly, D., Sáenz-Arroyo, A.,
1607 Sumaila, U. R., Wilson, R. W., Worm, B., & Castilla, J. C. (2017). Marine reserves can mitigate and promote
1608 adaptation to climate change. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of*
1609 *America*, 114(24), 6167–6175. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1701262114>

1610 Rogers A, Aburto-Oropeza O, Appeltans W, Assis J, Balance LT, Cury P, Duarte C, Favoretto F, Kumagai J, Lovelock C,
1611 Miloslavich P, Niamir A, Obura D, O’Leary BC, Reygondeau G, Roberts C, Sadovy de Mitcheson Y, Sutton T,
1612 Tittensor D, Velarde E (2020) Blue Paper 10: Critical Habitats and Biodiversity: Inventory, Thresholds, and
1613 Governance. Report prepared for the (Norwegian) Prime Minister’s High Level Panel on a Sustainable Ocean
1614 Economy. 85pp. [https://www.oceanpanel.org/blue-papers/critical-habitats-and-biodiversity-inventory-](https://www.oceanpanel.org/blue-papers/critical-habitats-and-biodiversity-inventory-thresholds-and-governance)
1615 [thresholds-and-governance](https://www.oceanpanel.org/blue-papers/critical-habitats-and-biodiversity-inventory-thresholds-and-governance)

1616 Roman, J. (2003). Whales Before Whaling in the North Atlantic. *Science*, 301(5632), 508–510.
1617 <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1084524>

1618 Roman, Joe, & McCarthy, J. J. (2010). The Whale Pump: Marine Mammals Enhance Primary Productivity in a Coastal
1619 Basin. *PLoS ONE*, 5(10), e13255. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0013255>

1620 Rosa, J. C. S., Sánchez, L. E., & Morrison-Saunders, A. (2018). Getting to ‘agreed’ post-mining land use – an ecosystem
1621 services approach. *Impact Assessment and Project Appraisal*, 36(3), 220–229.
1622 <https://doi.org/10.1080/14615517.2018.1445175>

1623 Ruggeri, G., Mazzocchi, C., & Corsi, S. (2020). Drinking biodiversity: A choice experiment on Franciacorta sparkling
1624 wines. *British Food Journal*, 122(8), 2531–2549. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BFJ-06-2019-0451>

1625 Sala, E., Mayorga, J., Bradley, D., Cabral, R. B., Atwood, T. B., Auber, A., Cheung, W., Costello, C., Ferretti, F.,
1626 Friedlander, A. M., Gaines, S. D., Garilao, C., Goodell, W., Halpern, B. S., Hinson, A., Kaschner, K., Kesner-
1627 Reyes, K., Leprieur, F., McGowan, J., ... Lubchenco, J. (2021). Protecting the global ocean for biodiversity, food
1628 and climate. *Nature*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-021-03371-z>

1629 Salles, JM., Teillard, F., Tichit, M. et al. Land sparing versus land sharing: an economist’s perspective. *Reg Environ*
1630 *Change* 17, 1455–1465 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-017-1142-4>

1631 Sanderman, J., Hengl, T., Fiske, G., Solvik, K., Adame, M. F., Benson, L., Bukoski, J. J., Carnell, P., Cifuentes-Jara, M.,
1632 Donato, D., Duncan, C., Eid, E. M., Ermgassen, P. zu, Lewis, C. J. E., Macreadie, P. I., Glass, L., Gress, S., Jardine,
1633 S. L., Jones, T. G., ... Landis, E. (2018). A global map of mangrove forest soil carbon at 30 m spatial resolution.
1634 *Environmental Research Letters*, 13(5), 055002. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/aabe1c>

1635 Sankaran, M., Augustine, D. J., & Ratnam, J. (2013). Native ungulates of diverse body sizes collectively regulate long-
1636 term woody plant demography and structure of a semi-arid savanna. *Journal of Ecology*, 101(6), 1389–1399.
1637 <https://doi.org/doi:10.1111/1365-2745.12147>

1638 Sannigrahi, S., Pilla, F., Basu, B., Basu, A. S., Zhang, Q., Wang, Y., Joshi, P. K., Chakraborti, S., Coscieme, L., Keesstra,
1639 S., Roy, P. S., & Sutton, P. C. (2020). Identification of Conservation Priority Zones Using Spatially Explicit Valued
1640 Ecosystem Services: A Case from the Indian Sundarbans. *Integrated Environmental Assessment and*
1641 *Management*, 16(5), 773–787. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ieam.4287>

1642 Sannigrahi, S., Zhang, Q., Joshi, P. K., Sutton, P. C., Keesstra, S., Roy, P. S., Pilla, F., Basu, B., Wang, Y., Jha, S., Paul, S.
1643 K., & Sen, S. (2020). Examining effects of climate change and land use dynamic on biophysical and economic
1644 values of ecosystem services of a natural reserve region. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 257, 120424.
1645 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.120424>

1646 SAPEA. (2017). Food from the oceans: How can more food and biomass be obtained from the oceans in a way that
1647 does not deprive future generations of their benefits>. [https://www.sapea.info/wp-](https://www.sapea.info/wp-content/uploads/FFOFINALREPORT.pdf)
1648 [content/uploads/FFOFINALREPORT.pdf](https://www.sapea.info/wp-content/uploads/FFOFINALREPORT.pdf)

1649 Sapkota, T.B., M.L. Jat, J.P. Aryal, R.K. Jat, and A. Khatri-Chhetri, 2015: Climate change adaptation, greenhouse gas
1650 mitigation and economic profitability of conservation agriculture: Some examples from cereal systems of
1651 Indo-Gangetic Plains. *J. Integr. Agric.*, 14, 1524–1533, doi:10.1016/S2095-3119(15)61093-0.

1652 Saunio, M., Bousquet, P., Poulter, B., Pregon, A., Ciais, P., Canadell, J. G., Dlugokencky, E. J., Etiope, G., Bastviken,
1653 D., Houweling, S., Janssens-Maenhout, G., Tubiello, F. N., Castaldi, S., Jackson, R. B., Alexe, M., Arora, V. K.,
1654 Beerling, D. J., Bergamaschi, P., Blake, D. R., ... Zhu, Q. (2016). The global methane budget 2000–2012. *Earth*
1655 *System Science Data*, 8(2), 697–751. <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-8-697-2016>

1656 Schaefer, H., Fletcher, S. E. M., Veidt, C., Lassey, K. R., Brailsford, G. W., Bromley, T. M., Dlugokencky, E. J., Michel, S.
1657 E., Miller, J. B., Levin, I., Lowe, D. C., Martin, R. J., Vaughn, B. H., & White, J. W. C. (2016). A 21st-century shift
1658 from fossil-fuel to biogenic methane emissions indicated by 13CH4. *Science*, 352(6281), 80–84.
1659 <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aad2705>

1660 Schimel, D., et al. (2015). Effect of increasing CO2 on the terrestrial carbon cycle. *Proceedings of the National*
1661 *Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 112(2): 436-441.
1662 <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1407302112>

1663 Schmitz, O. J., Wilmers, C. C., Leroux, S. J., Doughty, C. E., Atwood, T. B., Galetti, M., Davies, A. B., & Goetz, S. J.
1664 (2018). Animals and the zoogeochemistry of the carbon cycle. *Science*, 362(6419), eaar3213.
1665 <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aar3213>

1666 Schuldt, A., Assmann, T., Brezzi, M., Buscot, F., Eichenberg, D., Gutknecht, J., Härdtle, W., He, J.-S., Klein, A.-M., Kühn,
1667 P., Liu, X., Ma, K., Niklaus, P. A., Pietsch, K. A., Purahong, W., Scherer-Lorenzen, M., Schmid, B., Scholten, T.,
1668 Staab, M., ... Bruelheide, H. (2018). Biodiversity across trophic levels drives multifunctionality in highly diverse
1669 forests. *Nature Communications*, 9(1), 2989. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-018-05421-z>

1670 Schuur, E. A. G., Abbott, B., & the Permafrost Carbon Network. (2011). High risk of permafrost thaw. *Nature*,
1671 480(7375), 32–33. <https://doi.org/10.1038/480032a>

1672 Secretariat of the Convention on Biological Diversity. (2009). *Connecting Biodiversity and Climate Change Mitigation*
1673 *and Adaptation: Report of the Second Ad Hoc Technical Expert Group on Biodiversity and Climate Change*
1674 (Technical Series No. 41, p. 126).

1675 Secretariat of the Convention on Biological Diversity (2020) *Global Biodiversity Outlook 5*. Montreal.

1676 Shin, Yunne-Jai, Arneth, Almut, Chowdhury, Rinku Roy, Midgley, Guy F., Bukvareva, Elena, Heinemann, Andreas,
1677 Horcea-Milcu, Andra Ioana, Kolb, Melanie, Leadley, Paul, Oberdorff, Thierry, Pichs Madruga, Ramon,
1678 Rondinini, Carlo, Saito, Osamu, Sathyapalan, Jyothis, Bofo, Yaw Agyeman, Kindlmann, Pavel, Yue, Tianxiang,
1679 Krenova, Zdenka, & Osano, Philip. (2019). Plausible futures of nature, its contributions to people and their
1680 good quality of life. In *IPBES, 2019. Global Assessment on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services*. (p. 264).
1681 <https://www.ipbes.net/global-assessment>

1682 Shukla, P. R., Skea, J., Slade, R., van Diemen, R., Haughey, E., Malley, J., Pathak, M., & Portugal Pereira, J. (Eds.).
1683 (2019). Technical Summary. In *Climate Change and Land: An IPCC special report on climate change,*
1684 *desertification, land degradation, sustainable land management, food security, and greenhouse gas fluxes in*
1685 *terrestrial ecosystems* [P.R. Shukla, J. Skea, E. Calvo Buendia, V. Masson-Delmotte, H.-O. Pörtner, D. C.
1686 Roberts, P. Zhai, R. Slade, S. Connors, R. van Diemen, M. Ferrat, E. Haughey, S. Luz, S. Neogi, M. Pathak, J.
1687 Petzold, J. Portugal Pereira, P. Vyas, E. Huntley, K. Kissick, M, Belkacemi, J. Malley, (eds.)] (pp. 37–74).

1688 D.A. Siegel, T. DeVries, S.C. Doney, T. Bell (2021) Assessing the sequestration time scales of some ocean-based carbon
1689 dioxide reduction strategies. *Environ. Res. Lett.* in press <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ac0be0>

1690 Sileshi, G. W. (2016). The magnitude and spatial extent of influence of *Faidherbia albida* trees on soil properties and
1691 primary productivity in drylands. *Journal of Arid Environments*, 132, 1–14.
1692 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaridenv.2016.03.002>

1693 Smit, I. P., Asner, G. P., Govender, N., Vaughn, N. R., & van Wilgen, B. W. (2016). An examination of the potential
1694 efficacy of high-intensity fires for reversing woody encroachment in savannas. *Journal of Applied Ecology*,
1695 53(5), 1623–1633.

1696 Smith, P., Calvin, K., Nkem, J., Campbell, D., Cherubini, F., Grassi, G., Korotkov, V., Hoang, A. L., Lwasa, S., McElwee,
1697 P., Nkonya, E., Saigusa, N., Soussana, J. F., Taboada, M. A., Manning, F. C., Nampanzira, D., Arias-Navarro, C.,
1698 Vizzarri, M., House, J., ... Arneeth, A. (2020a). Which practices co-deliver food security, climate change
1699 mitigation and adaptation, and combat land degradation and desertification? *Global Change Biology*, 26(3),
1700 1532–1575. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.14878>

1701 Smith, T., Beagley, L., Bull, J. W., Milner-Gulland, E. J., Smith, M., Vorhies, F., & Addison, P. F. E. (2020b). Biodiversity
1702 means business: Reframing global biodiversity goals for the private sector. *Conservation Letters*, 13, e12690.
1703 <https://doi.org/10.1111/conl.12690>

1704 Soares-Filho, B., Moutinho, P., Nepstad, D., Anderson, A., Rodrigues, H., Garcia, R., Dietzsch, L., Merry, F., Bowman,
1705 M., Hissa, L., Silvestrini, R., & Maretti, C. (2010). Role of Brazilian Amazon protected areas in climate change
1706 mitigation. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 107(24), 10821–10826.
1707 <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0913048107>

1708 Sonter, L. J., Gordon, A., Archibald, C., Simmonds, J. S., Ward, M., Metzger, J. P., Rhodes, J. R., & Maron, M. (2020).
1709 Offsetting impacts of development on biodiversity and ecosystem services. *Ambio*, 49(4), 892–902.
1710 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-019-01245-3>

1711 Souster, T. A., Barnes, D. K. A., and Hopkins, J. (2020). Variation in zoobenthic blue carbon in the Arctic's Barents Sea
1712 shelf sediments. *Philos. Trans. R. Soc. A Math., Phys. Eng. Sci.* 378:20190362. doi: 10.1098/rsta.2019.0362

1713 Spahni, R., Joos, F., Stocker, B. D., Steinacher, M., & Yu, Z. C. (2013). Transient simulations of the carbon and nitrogen
1714 dynamics in northern peatlands: From the Last Glacial Maximum to the 21st century. *Climate of the Past*,
1715 9(3), 1287–1308. <https://doi.org/10.5194/cp-9-1287-2013>

1716 Spencer, T., Schuerch, M., Nicholls, R. J., Hinkel, J., Lincke, D., Vafeidis, A. T., Reef, R., McFadden, L., & Brown, S.
1717 (2016). Global coastal wetland change under sea-level rise and related stresses: The DIVA Wetland Change
1718 Model. *Global and Planetary Change*, 139, 15–30. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloplacha.2015.12.018>

1719 Stevens, N., Lehmann, C. E. R., Murphy, B. P., & Durigan, G. (2017). Savanna woody encroachment is widespread
1720 across three continents. *Global Change Biology*, 23(1), 235–244. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.13409>

1721 Strassburg, B. B. N., et al. (2010). Global congruence of carbon storage and biodiversity in terrestrial ecosystems.
1722 *Conservation Letters* 3(2): 98-105.

1723 Strassburg, B., Beyer, H., Crouzeilles, R., al, et, & Loyola, R. (2018). Strategic approaches to restoring ecosystems can
1724 triple conservation gains and halve costs. *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, 1, 64. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-018-0743-8>

1726 Sumaila, U. R., Ebrahim, N., Schuhbauer, A., Skerritt, D., Li, Y., Kim, H. S., Mallory, T. G., Lam, V. W. L., & Pauly, D.
1727 (2019). Updated estimates and analysis of global fisheries subsidies. *Marine Policy*, 109.
1728 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2019.103695>

1729 Sumaila, U. Rashid, Tai, T. C., Lam, V. W. Y., Cheung, W. W. L., Bailey, M., Cisneros-Montemayor, A. M., Chen, O. L.,
1730 & Gulati, S. S. (2019). Benefits of the Paris Agreement to ocean life, economies, and people. *Science Advances*,
1731 5(2), eaau3855. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.aau3855>

- 1732 Tamburini, G., Bommarco, R., Wanger, T. C., Kremen, C., van der Heijden, M. G. A., Liebman, M., & Hallin, S. (2020).
 1733 Agricultural diversification promotes multiple ecosystem services without compromising yield. *Science*
 1734 *Advances*, 6, eaba1715. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.aba1715>
- 1735 Tanentzap, A. J., & Coomes, D. A. (2012). Carbon storage in terrestrial ecosystems: Do browsing and grazing
 1736 herbivores matter? *Biological Reviews*, 87(1), 72–94. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-185X.2011.00185.x>
- 1737 Tarnocai, C., Canadell, J. G., Schuur, E. A. G., Kuhry, P., Mazhitova, G., & Zimov, S. (2009). Soil organic carbon pools
 1738 in the northern circumpolar permafrost region: SOIL ORGANIC CARBON POOLS. *Global Biogeochemical*
 1739 *Cycles*, 23(2), n/a-n/a. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2008GB003327>
- 1740 te Beest, M., Sitters, J., Ménard, C. B., & Olofsson, J. (2016). Reindeer grazing increases summer albedo by reducing
 1741 shrub abundance in Arctic tundra. *Environmental Research Letters*, 11(12), 125013.
 1742 <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/aa5128>
- 1743 Tessnow-von Wysocki I. and Vadrot ABM (2020) The Voice of Science on Marine Biodiversity Negotiations: A
 1744 Systematic Literature Review. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 7:614282. doi: 10.3389/fmars.2020.614282
- 1745 Tewari, P., Singh, R., Nagarkoti, P., & Gumber, S. (2020). Temporal Changes in Livelihood and Land Usage Patterns:
 1746 Case Study of a Primitive Tribe, Van Raji, from Uttarakhand, India (pp. 213–228).
 1747 https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-4712-6_13
- 1748 Thapa, S., Chitale, V., Rijal, S. J., Bisht, N., & Shrestha, B. B. (2018). Understanding the dynamics in distribution of
 1749 invasive alien plant species under predicted climate change in Western Himalaya. *PLOS ONE*, 13(4), e0195752.
 1750 <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0195752>
- 1751 Tian, H. Q., et al. (2020). A comprehensive quantification of global nitrous oxide sources and sinks. *Nature* 586(7828):
 1752 248+.
- 1753 Tittonell, P., Piñeiro, G., Garibaldi, L. A., Dogliotti, S., Oloff, H., & Jobbagy, E. G. (2020). Agroecology in Large Scale
 1754 Farming—A Research Agenda. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 4, 214.
 1755 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2020.584605>
- 1756 Tölle, M. H., Engler, S., & Panitz, H.-J. (2017). Impact of Abrupt Land Cover Changes by Tropical Deforestation on
 1757 Southeast Asian Climate and Agriculture. *Journal of Climate*, 30(7), 2587–2600. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI->
 1758 [D-16-0131.1](https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-16-0131.1)
- 1759 Townsend, P., & Masters, K. (2015). Lattice-work corridors for climate change: A conceptual framework for
 1760 biodiversity conservation and social-ecological resilience in a tropical elevational gradient. *Ecology and*
 1761 *Society*, 20. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-07324-200201>
- 1762 Trathan, P. N., Collins, M. A., Grant, S. M., Belchier, M., Barnes, D. K. A., Brown, J., & Staniland, I. (2014). The South
 1763 Georgia and the South Sandwich Islands MPA: Protecting A Biodiverse Oceanic Island Chain Situated in the
 1764 Flow of the Antarctic Circumpolar Current. *ADVANCES IN MARINE BIOLOGY*, 69, 15–78.
- 1765 Uddin, K., Chaudhary, S., Chettri, N., Kotru, R., Murthy, M., Chaudhary, R. P., Ning, W., Shrestha, S. M., & Gautam, S.
 1766 K. (2015). The changing land cover and fragmenting forest on the Roof of the World: A case study in Nepal's
 1767 Kailash Sacred Landscape. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 141, 1–10.
 1768 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2015.04.003>
- 1769 Uddin, Md. S., de Ruyter van Steveninck, E., Stuij, M., & Shah, M. A. R. (2013). Economic valuation of provisioning
 1770 and cultural services of a protected mangrove ecosystem: A case study on Sundarbans Reserve Forest,
 1771 Bangladesh. *Ecosystem Services*, 5, 88–93. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2013.07.002>
- 1772 UNEP. (2019, November 19). Emissions Gap Report 2019. UNEP - UN Environment Programme.
 1773 <http://www.unep.org/resources/emissions-gap-report-2019>
- 1774 UNEP-WCMC. (2021). The World Database on Protected Areas (WDPA).
 1775 <https://www.protectedplanet.net/en/thematic-areas/wdpa?tab=WDPA>

- 1776 UNESCO. 2021. Learn for our planet: A global review of how environmental issues are integrated in education. Paris,
1777 France
- 1778 United Nations, Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division. (2018). World Urbanization
1779 Prospects: The 2018 Revision (ST/ESA/SER.A/420). United Nations, Department of Economic and Social
1780 Affairs.
- 1781 United Nations Economist Network. (2020). Report of the UN Economist Network for the UN 75th Anniversary:
1782 Shaping the Trends of Our Time. United Nations.
- 1783 van Eijck, J., Romijn, H., Balkema, A., & Faaij, A. (2014). Global experience with jatropha cultivation for bioenergy:
1784 An assessment of socio-economic and environmental aspects. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*,
1785 32, 869–889. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2014.01.028>
- 1786 van Meijl, J. C. M., Havlík, P., Lotze-Campen, H., Stehfest, H., Witzke, P., Bodirsky, B., van Dijk, M., Doelman, M.,
1787 Humpenoeder, F., Levin-Koopman, J., Mueller, C., Popp, A., Tabeau, A. A., & Valin, H. (2017). Challenges of
1788 global agriculture in a climate change context by 2050: AgCLIM50 (I. Pérez Domínguez & T. Fellmann, Eds.).
1789 Publications Office. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/772445>
- 1790 van Wilgen, B. W., Forsyth, G. G., Le Maitre, D. C., Wannenburg, A., Kotzé, J. D., van den Berg, E., & Henderson, L.
1791 (2012). An assessment of the effectiveness of a large, national-scale invasive alien plant control strategy in
1792 South Africa. *Biological Conservation*, 148(1), 28–38.
- 1793 Vanbergen, A., Aizen, M., Cordeau, S., Garibaldi, L., Garratt, M., Kova'csHostya'nszki, A., Lecuyer, L., Ngo, H., Potts,
1794 S., Settele, J., et al. (2020). Transformation of agricultural landscapes in the Anthropocene: nature's
1795 contributions to people, agriculture and food security. *Adv. Ecol. Res.*
1796 <https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.aecr.2020.08.002>
- 1797 Vinya, R., Syampungani, S., Kasumu, E. C., Monde, C., & Kasubika, R. (2011). Preliminary study on the drivers of
1798 deforestation and potential for REDD+ in Zambia. Lusaka, Zambia: FAO/Zambian Ministry of Lands and
1799 Natural Resources.
- 1800 Vogt, M. A. B. (2020). Developing stronger association between market value of coffee and functional biodiversity.
1801 *Journal of Environmental Management*, 269, 110777. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2020.110777>
- 1802 Wanger, Thomas C., DeClerck, F., Garibaldi, L. A., Ghazoul, J., Kleijn, D., Klein, A.-M., Kremen, C., Mooney, H.,
1803 Perfecto, I., Powell, L. L., Settele, J., Solé, M., Tscharntke, T., & Weisser, W. (2020). Integrating agroecological
1804 production in a robust post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework. *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, 4(9), 1150–
1805 1152. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1262-y>
- 1806 Waycott, M., Duarte, C. M., Carruthers, T. J., Orth, R. J., Dennison, W. C., Olyarnik, S., Calladine, A., Fourqurean, J.
1807 W., Heck, K. L., & Hughes, A. R. (2009). Accelerating loss of seagrasses across the globe threatens coastal
1808 ecosystems. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 106(30), 12377–12381.
1809 <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0905620106>
- 1810 Weeks, R., Aliño, P. M., Atkinson, S., Beldia, P., Binson, A., Campos, W. L., Djohani, R., Green, A. L., Hamilton, R., &
1811 Horigue, V. (2014). Developing marine protected area networks in the Coral Triangle: Good practices for
1812 expanding the Coral Triangle Marine Protected Area System. *Coastal Management*, 42(2), 183–205.
1813 <https://doi.org/10.1080/08920753.2014.877768>
- 1814 West, T. A., Börner, J., & Fearnside, P. M. (2019). Climatic benefits from the 2006–2017 avoided deforestation in
1815 Amazonian Brazil. *Frontiers in Forests and Global Change*, 2, 52. <https://doi.org/10.3389/ffgc.2019.00052>
- 1816 Wigley, B. J., Augustine, D. J., Coetsee, C., Ratnam, J., & Sankaran, M. (2020). Grasses continue to trump trees at soil
1817 carbon sequestration following herbivore exclusion in a semiarid African savanna. *Ecology*, 101(5).
1818 <https://doi.org/10.1002/ecy.3008>
- 1819 Wilmers, C. C., Estes, J. A., Edwards, M., Laidre, K. L., & Konar, B. (2012). Do trophic cascades affect the storage and
1820 flux of atmospheric carbon? An analysis of sea otters and kelp forests. *Frontiers in Ecology and the*
1821 *Environment*, 10(8), 409–415. <https://doi.org/10.1890/110176>

- 1822 Wolf, J., Asrar, G. R., & West, T. O. (2017). Revised methane emissions factors and spatially distributed annual carbon
1823 fluxes for global livestock. *Carbon Balance and Management*, 12(1), 16. [https://doi.org/10.1186/s13021-017-](https://doi.org/10.1186/s13021-017-0084-y)
1824 0084-y
- 1825 Wong, N. H., Cheong, D. K. W., Yan, H., Soh, J., Ong, C. L., & Sia, A. (2003). The effects of rooftop garden on energy
1826 consumption of a commercial building in Singapore. *Energy and Buildings*, 35(4), 353–364.
1827 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-7788\(02\)00108-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-7788(02)00108-1)
- 1828 World Health Organization. (2016). Urban green spaces and health. WHO Regional Office for Europe.
- 1829 Xi, Y., Peng, S., Ciais, P., & Chen, Y. (2020). Future impacts of climate change on inland Ramsar wetlands. *Nature*
1830 *Climate Change*, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-020-00942-2>
- 1831 Xiao, X., Agustí, S., Lin, F., Li, K., Pan, Y., Yu, Y., Zheng, Y., Wu, J., & Duarte, C. (2017). Nutrient removal from Chinese
1832 coastal waters by large-scale seaweed aquaculture. *Scientific Reports*, 7, 46613.
1833 <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep46613>
- 1834 Yu, K. (2020, July 30). Sponge City: Leveraging Nature As Ecological Infrastructure. CLC Webinar Series: Cities
1835 Adapting to a Disrupted World. <https://www.clc.gov.sg/events/webinars/view/sponge-cities>
- 1836 Yusuf, H. M., Treydte, A. C., & Sauerborn, J. (2015). Managing Semi-Arid Rangelands for Carbon Storage: Grazing and
1837 Woody Encroachment Effects on Soil Carbon and Nitrogen. *PLOS ONE*, 10(10), e0109063.
1838 <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0109063>
- 1839 Zhang, G., Xiao, X., Dong, J., Xin, F., Zhang, Y., Qin, Y., Doughty, R., & Moore, B. (2020). Fingerprint of rice paddies in
1840 spatial–temporal dynamics of atmospheric methane concentration in monsoon Asia. *Nature*
1841 *Communications*, 11, 554. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-14155-5>
- 1842 Zhu, Z., Piao, S., Myneni, R., Huang, M., Zeng, Z., Canadell, J., Ciais, P., Sitch, S., Friedlingstein, P., Arneth, A., Cao, C.,
1843 Cheng, L., Kato, E., Koven, C., Li, Y., Lian, X., Liu, Y., Liu, R., Mao, J., & Zeng, N. (2016). Greening of the Earth
1844 and its drivers. *Nature Climate Change*, 6. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate3004>
- 1845 Zomer, R., & Oli, K. P. (2011). Kailash sacred landscape conservation initiative – Feasibility assessment report.
1846 ICIMOD.
- 1847